

Traffic Density Based Traffic Signal Control System

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Dedication

I dedicate my work to my family and many friends wholeheartedly. A special feeling of gratitude to my loving parents and my brother whose words of encouragement and push for tenacity ring in my ears. I also dedicate this work to my group members who have supported me throughout the process. I will always appreciate all they have done. I dedicate this work and give special thanks to my best friend Sadia Haque Ripti, for being there for me throughout the entire capstone project. You have been my best cheerleader. All my efforts would be inadequate without the assistance of our respected supervisor Dr. Mohammed Moseeur Rahman Sir.

- *Md. Ikrum Hussain*

I would like to dedicate this work to Allah, my honorable supervisor, my parents and my team members. First of all, Allah always helps us to complete our work. Our respected supervisor Dr. Mohammed Moseeur Rahman Sir always guides us and encourages us to complete our work perfectly. We would like to dedicate our work to our supervisor.

- Abdullah Al Noman

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- Sonat Ghosh

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- Shahriar Khan

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report details the development of a "Traffic Density Based Traffic Signal Control System" aimed at alleviating the significant traffic congestion in the Dhaka Metropolitan Region. The project proposes an innovative approach to traffic management through the deployment of a dynamic signal control system that adapts to real-time traffic conditions. The primary objective is to enhance urban mobility, safety, and overall traffic flow efficiency by utilizing Digital Image Processing (DSP) and ultrasonic sensors for continuous monitoring and adaptive signal control. The current fixed-timer and manual traffic control methods are insufficient, leading to inefficiencies and delays, particularly during peak traffic periods. The system's core technology integrates DSP and ultrasonic sensors to measure traffic density and adjust signal timings accordingly. The prototype developed employs NVIDIA Jetson Nano, cameras, Arduino Nano, and various sensors to create a responsive and adaptive traffic control system. This prototype has been rigorously tested to meet predefined performance metrics. Economic analyses, including cost assessments and Net Present Value (NPV) calculations, affirm the project's feasibility and potential for significant impact. The anticipated benefits include reduced congestion, enhanced road safety, and a more efficient urban transportation system, ultimately leading to improved commuter experiences and economic productivity. The report underscores the necessity of transitioning to advanced traffic management solutions to address the growing urbanization and vehicle proliferation, ensuring a sustainable and efficient urban mobility framework for the future. This project is expected to not only improve traffic conditions but also set a precedent for similar initiatives in other urban areas facing traffic congestion challenges.

PART-A

This part contains the concept and the project proposal as prepared on EEE400A.

Chapter 1 Project Concept and Proposal

1.1 Project Introduction

In the pursuit of enhancing urban mobility and addressing the challenges associated with growing traffic congestion, the current initiative is dedicated to revolutionizing traffic management within the Dhaka Metropolitan Region. With a firm commitment to resolving the pressing concerns surrounding traffic control, this initiative sets forth a comprehensive strategy encompassing multiple targets. The paramount aim of this project includes the significant improvement of traffic safety, the optimization of traffic flow dynamics, and the seamless integration of sophisticated congestion density measurement systems. The project is driven by a clear understanding of the flaws in the current method for controlling traffic signals. In the present, the usual way to deal with traffic congestion is to have traffic police on the road. During times of heavy traffic, these hardworking officers physically direct the flow of cars by using hand signs to tell drivers when to go and when to stop. However, this method is less effective when there is a lot of traffic at a crossing. The fixed-timer traffic signal model is one of the least used on roads. We could solve this problem to a substantial extent by deploying this density-based traffic control system using Digital Image Processing (DSP) and Obstacles detection sensors like Ultra-sonic sensor system to continuously manage traffic lights. The traffic management initiative has set specific goals for addressing critical challenges and improving urban mobility. The inadequacies of the current traffic signal control system drive the key aims of improving traffic safety and perfecting traffic flow. The project intends to combat traffic congestion effectively by using innovative technology and congestion density inspection technologies.

During an emergency, special attention will be paid to the movement of ambulances and VIP vehicles. The initiative aims to set up a seamless and efficient transportation network that helps all commuters and ensures smoother traffic flow by strategically

perfecting red-light delays and right-lane timings. We expect that our project will ease the suffering of commuters on the road.

1.2 Literature review

Our proposed technology aims to enhance the traffic system in areas with heavy traffic loads. The phenomenon of perceiving traffic is commonly observed. The maintenance of the trail's priority is determined by its density. The obstruction calculation algorithm relies on the utilization of real-time live video frames accompanied by citation images. Furthermore, the presence of automobiles in the desired vicinity is also a significant factor. Our project is designed to effectively manage VIP movement and respond to emergency situations. Numerous scholarly articles have extensively examined this topic.

Mittal et al. 2023 introduce **EnsembleNet: a hybrid approach for vehicle detection and estimation of traffic density based on faster R-CNN and YOLO models** [1]. Their work involves the collection of data from many open-source libraries, such as MB7500, KITTI, and FLIR. Vehicle classification has been achieved using the process of image annotation. Several data augmentation techniques are employed to enhance the size of the dataset and address the issue of class imbalance. The sharpening process has resulted in an improvement in image quality. Subsequently, a hybridized model incorporating elements of Faster R-CNN and YOLO has been trained on pre-processed data, employing a majority voting classifier. The findings of the proposed model have been compared with those of its base estimators using the collected datasets. The suggested model has exhibited a detection accuracy of 98%, surpassing the performance of YOLO and Faster R-CNN, which achieve accuracies of 95.8% and 97.5%, respectively.

Gandhi et al. 2020 introduce a conference paper named **Smart Control of Traffic Light Using Artificial Intelligence**[2]. The method under consideration involves the utilization of live images obtained from closed-circuit television (CCTV) cameras installed at traffic intersections. These images are used to calculate real-time traffic density by detecting the number of cars present at the signal. Then, the green signal duration is adjusted accordingly. To obtain an accurate estimation of the green signal time, vehicles are divided into four classifications: cars, bikes, buses/trucks, and rickshaws. The system employs the YOLO algorithm to accurately identify and quantify the number of cars present. Subsequently, it adjusts the timing of the traffic signal based on the density of vehicles in the respective direction. The signal-switching algorithm utilizes the density of traffic, in conjunction with other relevant data, to determine the duration of the green signal timer for each lane. The duration of the red signal periods is adjusted accordingly. A simulation is developed to illustrate the efficacy of the system and to make a comparison with the current static system.

Albatish et al. 2019 Worked on **Modeling and Controlling Smart Traffic Light System Using a Rule Based System**[3]. The problem of traffic lights is a complex problem which they have designed hardware to solve. The hardware tracks lane congestion and records cases in a text file, which it then sends to an expert system tool that analyses the cases at junctions and determines the entire cycle time considering the intersection instances. The choice is then put into action by the expert system tool by sending a text file to the hardware. The expert system tool is represented by CLIPS language and the hardware is represented by Arduino UNO. Infrared Radiation (IR) sensors and Arduino make up the expert system's hardware. The IR sensors oversee keeping an eye on the level of traffic. There are 4 IRs in use. There is a single IR sensor in each lane. Depending on the kind of traffic at the junction, the distance between the

sensor and the stop line will change. These sensors will detect any traffic that is present in that specific lane. According to the lane width, the sensors' sensitivity to the car is tuned. If a car is in the lane, the IR will broadcast radiation and receive it back. If a vehicle is present, the IR will transmit logic 1 to the Arduino; otherwise, it will send logic 0.

Vogel et al. 2018 introduced **Improving Traffic Light Control by Means of Fuzzy Logic**[4]. The researchers put forth a system based on Arduino-UNO and using Fuzzy Logic, to reduce traffic congestion and minimize waiting time. The present system utilizes the camera to capture images, which are subsequently processed in MATLAB. During the processing stage, the images are transformed into threshold images by eliminating saturation and colors. Subsequently, the system calculates the traffic density. The connection between Arduino and MATLAB is established through the utilization of USB and simulation packages that come preloaded. The duration of the green light for each lane is determined by Arduino, taking into consideration factors such as traffic count and traffic density. Nevertheless, this approach exhibits various limitations. The vehicles frequently exhibit overlapping patterns, rendering the task of accurately quantifying the number of cars on the road challenging. Furthermore, the detection process was impeded by the presence of other items, which were also subjected to black-and-white conversion. Consequently, it became difficult to differentiate between ordinary objects such as billboards, poles, trees, with vehicles.

Javaid et al. 2018 proposed a paper **Smart traffic management system using Internet of Things**[5]. The system under consideration has been developed to manage traffic flow inside road networks. This is achieved through the utilization of several technologies, including sensors, surveillance cameras, and RFIDs that are strategically placed along the sides of the roadways. The system operates in a distributed fashion, where it handles the data from sensors at the node level and processes the data from videos at the local server. It utilizes cumulative density calculations to effectively

manage traffic based on the density levels. Furthermore, it addresses emergency vehicles such as ambulances and fire brigades. Additionally, this feature aids users in acquiring information regarding the congestion status of a road through predictive analysis.

Udoakah et al. 2017 publish a paper called, **Design and implementation of a density-based traffic light control with surveillance system**[6]. Their concept was that they detect the car's number by IR sensor and measure the density of the road. For that, they used Sensors Arrays, Controller, DC Power Supply, etc. In this paper, they used Proteus 7 for simulation. The sensors on each lane of traffic were represented by switches because the Proteus software does not include an infrared sensor representation. One lane has 4 switches representing the infrared sensor. The switches on each lane of traffic and the LEDs which represent the traffic indicator of each lane are divided into four and are controlled by the pins of the microcontroller. To control the traffic light indicators, they used microcontrollers. The infrared sensor arrays for each of the four lanes are represented by the labeled switches spaced at regular intervals. The infrared sensors are a set of four switches that are installed in each lane. The statuses of all the sensor arrays on each lane of traffic are read once the traffic control system is operational and are then sent as input to the microcontroller for logical operations. Each lane is given a unique serial number by the system, which gives lane one to the lane with the highest density. To prepare for passing traffic in that lane and to allow for a little delay before issuing the go signal with the GREEN light, the system sets the ready flag for lane one when the YELLOW light is shown.

Rani et al. 2017 introduced **DYNAMIC TRAFFIC MANAGEMENT SYSTEM USING INFRARED (IR) AND INTERNET OF THINGS (IoT)**[7]. They intend to put their "Proof-of-Concept" prototype, which incorporates traffic lights, IR sensors, a Wi-Fi transmitter, and a Raspberry Pi microprocessor, into action at one intersection. The Wi-Fi transmitter sends the perceived information obtained from the IR sensor, which

the Raspberry Pi controller then receives. The user receives a notification of the signal's status as he travels and the waiting time for the signal is constantly adjusted based on the data. As a central console, the Raspberry Pi controller chooses which side of the traffic signals should be opened or closed. To reduce complexity, traffic lights are opened and closed in a clockwise direction. The sensors are interfaced with the Raspberry-pi Board, which has been configured to send information to the traffic lights and alert mobile devices. The input data from the IR sensors is wholly dependent on the time split. They also mention how additional potential distractions for the IR sensors may be avoided by utilizing an image processing system with a webcam placed near the signal.

Hasan et al. 2014 present a paper called **Smart Traffic Control System with Application of Image Processing Techniques**[8]. Their concept was that instead of counting the number of cars, they calculated traffic density, which is equivalent to the entire area occupied by vehicles on the road in terms of the total number of pixels in a video frame. They applied the background subtraction method to complete this task. Under this, they used two types of methods simultaneously to find traffic density: one is gradient magnitude, and another is direct subtraction. The direct subtraction method may not be able to detect a black vehicle. However, there are some circumstances in which the Gradient Magnitude method's detected edges may not provide a closed contour. So, they applied both methods simultaneously. They used MATLAB for image processing, the ATMEGA8 microcontroller for controlling traffic lights, and the USART (Universal Synchronous Asynchronous Receiver Transmitter) module for sending control information to the microcontroller.

Kanungo et al. 2014 developed a model of **Smart Traffic Light Switching and Traffic Density Calculation using Video Processing**[9]. This study describes a technique for calculating traffic density in real-time utilizing video and image processing using live video feed from cameras at traffic intersections. Their system uses video cameras on

either side of traffic intersections to simulate a four-way intersection. Four video cameras will therefore be mounted above the red lights that face the road. To compute the number of vehicles on each side of the road and use an algorithm to turn the traffic lights appropriately, cameras would record video and relay it to servers. In terms of hardware, these cameras must be connected to the server to get a live feed, as well as a server powerful enough to handle the processing demands. The system makes use of the MATLAB video and image processing toolkit as well as a C++ compiler to provide algorithmic results. The number of automobiles is not provided by their system. The benefit of calculating vehicle density is the amount of time a truck will take to pass the light, which would be equivalent to the total amount of time two cars will take one after the other.

Chen et al. 2011 propose a paper called **A Real-Time Vision System for Nighttime Vehicle Detection and Traffic Surveillance**[10]. This research study presents efficient methods for detecting, tracking, and identifying vehicles during nighttime traffic surveillance. The proposed methodologies involve analyzing the geographical and temporal characteristics of vehicle lights. The system includes a rapid bright-object segmentation procedure, a connected-component analysis algorithm, a spatial clustering technique, and a feature-based methodology for tracking and identifying vehicles. This approach enhances the accuracy of detection outcomes by addressing faults and occlusions from noise and errors. The experimental findings demonstrate the system's feasibility and effectiveness in detecting and identifying vehicles in different nighttime settings. However, the efficacy of these techniques is constrained by the volume of cars passing through the designated areas, making them difficult to employ for tasks such as vehicle categorization, velocity determination, and motion analysis.

1.2.1 Literature Survey

Table 1.1 Survey of Strength, Weakness and Limitations of Literature Review

Year	Authors	Approach	Strength / Outcome	Weakness and Limitations
2023	Mittal et al[1]	EnsembleNet	The proposed model achieves 98% detection accuracy, outperforming YOLO and Faster R-CNN. Enhanced traffic density estimation compared to YOLO and Faster R-CNN.	Absence of detailed information on the impact of dataset characteristics, such as diversity, size, and quality, on the performance of the proposed hybrid model.
2020	Gandhi et al[2]	YOLO version no. 07	The system shows a 23% improvement in vehicles crossing intersections. Proposed adaptive system consistently outperforms static system in traffic distribution.	High maintenance cost for photoelectric sensors in traffic control system.
2019	Albatish et al[3]	Traffic Lights Expert System (TLES), Rule-based system (RBS)	Developed Traffic Lights Expert System (TLES) for dynamic cycle time allocation	Traditional methods fail in traffic congestion situations. Imperfections in sensors can affect the system's accuracy.
2018	Vogel et al[4]	Fuzzy logic	Major improvement in high traffic demand scenarios for primary driveways. Fuzzy logic system reduced pollution and improved traffic parameters	Fuzzy system favors primary driveways, affecting secondary driveways negatively. Disproportion in fuzzy rules inevitable due to limited signal phases.
2018	Javaid et al[5]	IoT based	Utilizing the Internet of Things and a decentralized approach to optimize road traffic and manage traffic situations more accurately	Limited to a prototype.
2017	Udoakah et al[6]	Microcontroller Based	Traffic light systems outperformed conventional systems in controlling traffic. PIC18F4550 microcontroller with infrared sensors improved traffic flow efficiency.	Infrared sensors are disturbed by noise but are affordable and available. Proteus software lacks infrared sensor representation for accurate simulation

2017	Rani et al[7]	IoT, IR, and Image Processing	Dynamic traffic management system reduces congestion and waiting time. IR sensors and image processing enhance traffic signal control efficiency.	Waiting time for vehicles on less congested side due to time split. Existing models using Arduino boards have limited physical object handling capability. Geographical nature and road conditions affect usability and cost of models.
2014	Hasan et al[8]	MATLAB, Microcontroller Based	Traffic density measured by total area occupied by vehicles on roads.	Total area occupied by vehicles on the road in terms of total pixels in a video frame. Unable to count vehicles.
2014	Kanungo et al[9]	Image Processing, Real - Time Video	Compared to a hard-coded system, a dynamically written algorithm increased traffic flow by 35%. 4-5 times less traffic, providing more room for cars to move. The suggested technique reduces air pollution, fuel consumption, and accidents.	Hard-coded lights, constant maintenance, and high hardware costs are limitations. Pressure mats and infrared sensors have higher installation and maintenance costs
2011	Chen et al[10] US Patent No. 9185363	Image Processing and Embedded System	The proposed system effectively detects and classifies vehicles in nighttime traffic scenes. The system tracks moving cars and motorbikes using spatial clustering and tracking. Comparative results show successful vehicle detection in various environmental conditions.	potential errors caused by occlusions, noise, and errors in the bright-object segmentation and spatial classification processes

1.3 Standards and codes of practices

The focus of our project pertains to the field of traffic signaling. The provision of traffic signal manuals in Bangladesh is facilitated by the Bangladesh Road Transport Authority (BRTA). The manual provided by them has been considered for our project. Several key aspects are mentioned below.

1.3.1 Design and Mounting of Signal Heads

The recommended minimum diameter for standard signal lenses is 200mm, but 300mm is desired, particularly in the context of big and heavily trafficked intersections. The minimum diameter requirement for lenses on arrow signals, pedestrian signals, and overhead-mounted signals is 300mm. To enhance visibility, it is recommended that the signal lamps be affixed onto a backing board of black color. Additionally, the lamps should be equipped with hoods to prevent their visibility from drivers approaching from other directions.

Fig. 1.1 Traffic signals for the control of vehicular traffic at road junctions.

The signal sequence is RED-AMBER-GREEN and then back to RED.

The optimal positioning of signal heads on vertical posts involves mounting them at a height of approximately 2.3 meters above the surface of the carriageway. The appropriate positioning of the signal is adjacent to the kerb or the edge of the carriageway, while ensuring there is ample space to prevent any contact between the signal head and passing cars. The signals should be fixed overhead with the lowest edge positioned at a height of 5.7 meters above the carriageway

The signal sequence is RED-AMBER-GREEN and then back to RED.

APPLICATION: Traffic signals are used to control conflicting streams of traffic at a junction to minimize delay and reduce accidents.

VARIATION: In cases when the signals are positioned above the carriageway, it is possible for the signal lamps to be arranged in a horizontal manner, as depicted in the illustration provided. It is important to observe that the red signal lamp should consistently be positioned at the right-hand end.

1.4 Stakeholders' expectations/requirements

Individuals or organizations who are actively participating in the project or whose interests may be affected positively or negatively because of project execution or successful project completion are considered stakeholders. For our project, we considered seven sorts of stakeholders

These stakeholders are:

1. Pedestrians
2. Vehicle Owners/ Drivers (Including Car, Bus, CNG, Rickshaw, Cycle, and Motorcycle)
3. City Corporation/ Local Municipal
4. Dhaka Transport Coordination Authority

5. Dhaka Metropolitan Police, Dhaka
6. Bangladesh Road Transport Authority

We learned about their needs after speaking with them. The requirements are listed below.

1. **Pedestrians:**

At first, we talked with several pedestrians on the road, and we also tried to understand their needs. The requirements that we have come to know after taking a survey in person are given below:

- Ensure clear visual cues when it is safe to cross the street, such as signs and lighting.
- Include emergency buttons that enable pedestrians to instantly initiate the pedestrian phase and, if necessary, stop vehicular traffic.
- Enough time to cross the street safely.

On a scale of 1 to 5, they rate the current traffic situation as 1(ineffective).

2. **Vehicle Owners/Drivers (Including Car, Bus, CNG, Rickshaw, Cycle, and Motorcycle):**

For our survey, we went to some Owners/Drivers and conducted them in person. They claimed that on their everyday journey, they are dissatisfied with the current traffic signaling system. A properly synchronized traffic signaling system is desired by all car owners. They have also reported that traffic signals are not functioning properly. They ranked the present traffic system as 1(very poor), on a scale of 1-5. They favor lanes with shorter wait times and more advanced traffic signal systems. They proposed requirements which are:

- Faster Traffic movement.
- Less congestion on the road.
- More visible traffic lights.

- Add a timer display alongside traffic lights.
- Ensure all safety issues.

3. **City Corporation/ Local Municipal:**

We engaged in discussions with the assistant engineer specializing in civil engineering at the Traffic Engineering Circle of Dhaka South City Corporation, as well as the engineer specializing in electrical and electronic engineering at the Traffic Engineering Circle of Dhaka North City Corporation. The points highlighted by DNCC are as follows:

- The system should be cost-effective.
- Easy to monitor and control.
- Control the traffic properly.
- Not to make the signal green for more than 2 minutes.
- Police boxes enable manual traffic signal changes in emergencies.
- The current traffic system was assessed as 1 (extremely inadequate) on a rating scale ranging from 1 to 5.

4. **Dhaka Transport Coordination Authority:**

We actively participated in a discussion with the Senior Road Safety Specialist, Assistant Engineer, and Junior Civil Engineer of Dhaka Transport Coordination Authority (DTCA). DTCA is an organization actively involved in the implementation of the Dhaka Integrated Traffic Management Project (DITMP) as a pilot initiative. We have obtained several technological insights as outlined below.

- Technical components must be waterproof.
- Incorporate Non-Motorized Vehicles (NMVs) in density measurement.
- Increase the number of individual sensors to measure traffic density.
- Design traffic signals following BRTA Manual guidelines.

On a scale that ranged from 1 to 5, they rated the current traffic system as a 1 (extremely inadequate).

5. Dhaka Metropolitan Police, Dhaka:

We talked with the Inspector(admin) of the Traffic Ramna Division. When we spoke with him, it seemed like they were quite dissatisfied with the traffic signal control system. At present time they are controlling the traffic signals on the road by Traffic Police. By talking with them we get to know that they are quite dissatisfied with the traffic signal control system. They have several complaints about the present traffic light management system. According to them:

- Unawareness of traffic signals among drivers and the public.
- Increase public awareness of traffic signals and road rules.
- Education is crucial for decongesting Bangladesh's roads.
- They said that the current traffic management system is in handling traffic flow and ensuring road safety as 1(Not effective at all), on a ranking of 1-5.

6. Bangladesh Road Transport Authority:

The Bangladesh Road Transport Authority (BRTA) is a government agency responsible for regulating and overseeing the road transport sector in Bangladesh. Established in 1987, the BRTA plays a crucial role in ensuring road safety, issuing driving licenses, registering vehicles, and enforcing traffic rules and regulations. With its headquarters in Dhaka, the BRTA operates through various regional and district offices across the country to effectively manage and maintain a safe and efficient road transport system.

After conducting an in-person survey with the Assistant Director engineer and Deputy Director of BRTA. We have acquired multiple insights, which are outlined as follows.

- BRTA collaborates with the City Corporation, Traffic Police, and DTCA for improved traffic.

- Will introduce a new traffic signal manual for widespread implementation.
- They ranked the present traffic system as 1(Very Poor), on a scale of 1-5.

1.5 Project requirements

The project specifications for a traffic density-based traffic signal control system may encompass a diverse range of technical and functional components. We have diligently considered the feedback and input provided by all stakeholders to fulfill the requirements of our project.

1. **Traffic Data Collection:** The system shall be capable of collecting real-time traffic data, including information on vehicle density, speed, and count, through the utilization of sensors, cameras, or other suitable technological means.
2. **Data Processing and Analysis:** The data obtained should be processed and analyzed by the system to ascertain the level of traffic density at every intersection or stretch of route.
3. **Density Limit and Triggers:** The density limits, which cause changes in the timing of traffic lights, are the exact numbers of vehicles that cause the timing of traffic signals to change. The goal of this study is to find the most effective levels of traffic that cause light phases to need to be changed.
4. **Emergency Vehicle Priority:** Implement a feature that possesses the ability to differentiate emergency vehicles and optimize signal timing to ensure their timely and unhindered passage.

5. **Scalability:** The architecture of the system should prioritize scalability, allowing for its effective deployment across various crossings and road networks.
6. **Performance Metrics and Reporting:** Performance metrics evaluate the effectiveness and efficiency of a system or process, such as reduced waiting times, congestion, and improved traffic flow. They serve as objective criteria for assessing transportation systems' success and enabling comparisons and analysis of strategies. Implementing reporting systems is crucial for monitoring and assessing the system's influence on traffic conditions.
7. **Training and Support:** Provide thorough training and support to traffic engineers, operators, and maintenance personnel with the aim of improving their competence in utilizing and supervising the system.

1.6 Project Management

1.6.1 *Project plan*

Any project must include planning because it directs a team through the entire procedure. It helps to set desired objectives, analyze project risk, estimate the budget, and produce satisfactory results.

Project Plan

1. Project selection.
2. Initial research and discussion with supervisor.
3. Literature Review
4. Identifying standards and codes of practice
5. Identifying Stakeholders
6. Creating a questionnaire for Stakeholders

7. Response collection from stakeholders [Milestone 1]
8. Finalizing project requirement
9. Project Planning
10. Risk management
11. Preparing the resource list [Milestone 2]
12. Analyzing the budget
13. Investigation of the project product lifecycle
14. Analyzing environmental impact and sustainability, health and safety issues, and impact on society.
15. Creating project proposal paper [Milestone 3]
16. Evaluation of the project's initial design
17. Multiple solutions analysis [Milestone 4]
18. Finalizing the simulation part of the project [Milestone 5]
19. Analysis of system performance
20. The formation of prototypes [Milestone 6]
21. Performance evaluation of the implemented system [Milestone 7]
22. Submission of design report [Milestone 8]
23. Finalization of the prototype
24. Demonstration of the project
25. Economic analysis
26. Preparing final report and presentation [Milestone 9]

Table 1.2 Project Activity Lists.

Activity No.	Activities	Duration [Days]	Predecessor	No. of Worker
A.	Project selection	14	-	4
B.	Initial research and discussion with the supervisor	3	A	4
C.	Literature Review	7	B	4

D.	Identifying standards and codes of practice	4	B	2
E.	Identifying Stakeholders	2	C, D	4
F.	Creating a questionnaire for Stakeholders	5	E	4
G.	Response collection from stakeholders [Milestone 1]	3	F	4
H.	Finalizing project requirement	3	G	2
I.	Project Planning	5	H	
J.	Risk management	3	I	2
K.	Preparing the resource list [Milestone 2]	4	I	2
L.	Analyzing the budget and Projected product lifecycle	2	K	
M.	Analyzing environmental impact and sustainability, health and safety issues, and impact on society.	4	I	2
N.	Creating project proposal paper [Milestone 3]	15	J, L, M	4
O.	Evaluation of the project's initial design	7	N	4
P.	Multiple solutions analysis [Milestone 4]	5	O	4
Q.	Finalizing the simulation part of the project [Milestone 5]	12	P	4
R.	Analysis of system performance	20	Q	4
S.	The formation of prototypes [Milestone 6]	34	R	4
T.	Performance evaluation of the implemented system [Milestone 7]	20	S	4
U.	Submission of design report [Milestone 8]	22	T	4
V.	Finalization of the prototype	25	U	4
W.	Demonstration of the project	37	V	4

X.	Economic analysis	10	W	4
Y.	Preparing final report and presentation [Milestone 9]	25	X	4

1.6.1.1 CPM

Critical path: A, B, C, E, F, G, H, I, K, L, N, O, P, Q, R, S, T, U, V, W, X, Y

Non-critical path: D, J, M

Total project completion time: 280 Days.

1.6.1.2 Gantt Chart:

Fig. 1.2 Gantt Chart.

For Better view:

<https://app.ganttpro.com/shared/token/f0dfd5ef6af905944c99a9e1e958b695f7a821a0d1561c701e7fbc0dc710bc94/1198113>

1.6.2 *Risk management*

Risk can be defined as the state of uncertainty that surrounds the potential consequences or implications of any endeavor involving assets, with a particular focus on unfavorable or undesirable outcomes. The identification and management of project issues are contingent on studying risks and implementing mitigation and contingency measures. The timely execution of critical risk mitigation measures can be achieved by promptly identifying possible hazards at the project's onset. We have also observed specific issues that could potentially impede our endeavors in this undertaking. Furthermore, we have identified their strategies for mitigating risks and implementing backup plans.

1. **Technical Risks:** These risks are related to the technology and tools being used in the project. We will design our whole project in software, and we will simulate it. The project design will be at risk if the selected software is missing a few essential features that are necessary for our project. A risk for our project would also exist if the software provider stopped supporting the version of the program we chose. These risks may create a delay in the start of our project design, which will impact on our 5th and 8th milestones. We will have to use different software to mitigate these risks. Additionally, we will look for similar data or information for the simulation if we are unable to find the right data or information for our project in any system. Now come to the hardware implementation, A risk may arise. While using the equipment, we can have technical issues or may damage any of our equipment. Our sixth milestone will be delayed due to this risk. We might have to quickly repurchase the equipment from the neighborhood or online market to mitigate the risk.
2. **Schedule Risks:** Our group members might face some critical health issues or family problems. Which will affect our project schedule. As we have started

our project, if any of our group members face any health issues, we will need to divide our work among other members. To mitigate the fiscal crisis faced during the project, the other members will share the rest of the amount in the project. And if any group member gets sick, unfortunately, we will reschedule our project activity list and complete the project on time.

3. **Cost Risks:** The price of electrical items varies a lot in the present market. Because of the fluctuating situation, the cost of the components, labor costs, and other miscellaneous costs may increase, for which our budget may be affected. To mitigate the unavailability of project components, we may need to go to the local markets and buy the project components to reduce the unavailability of such components. To keep costs lower, we must purchase all the components at once.
4. **Stakeholder risk:** After the initial design plan and main analysis, we would need feedback from additional stakeholders. We will reschedule to work on tasks that are unrelated to their ideas if there are delays in getting this feedback. We will immediately begin stakeholder-dependent initiatives and other actions in parallel after receiving feedback from the stakeholders. If we are unable to get feedback, we shall base our goal setting on the established functional requirements.

1.6.3 Required resources and budget

Before we can start working on our project, we need to first make a prototype. This will involve utilizing simulation software to model the functionality and design of our project. Subsequently, we will proceed to the physical construction phase. To engage in these tasks, it will be necessary to utilize various forms of computational and

simulation software. In addition, the fabrication of the device necessitates the utilization of several types of equipment.

The pricing for the equipment was estimated using online stores. Even though we establish the pricing of the equipment based on internet stores, the costs of the equipment in the local market exhibit a proximity to those found in online shops.

In contrast, prototype development incurs additional expenses like travel, labor, transportation, and other related costs.

Table 1.3 Estimated Budget list.

Equipment Name	Quantity	Quantity Price (TK)	Price (Taka)	Justifications
Nvidia Jetson Nano 4GB	1	30,990	30,990	Conducting machine learning models to analyze vehicle density.
Arduino Nano	5	600	3,000	To receive the data from the sensors, process it, and control the traffic lights in real-time
Camera	4	4539.25	18,157	Video recording of intersection to analyze density.
IR Transmitter & Receiver	20	30	600	To sense the vehicle.
LED(RGY)	12	350	4,200	Will be used for traffic signs (Red, Amber & Green)
DC generator	1	3,000	3,000	Will be used as a source of power.
Wire	100m	10	1,000	To do the electrical connection.

Electric Cable for Camera	100m	15	1,500	To collect images from the road.
Subtotal Cost			62,447	
Travel Cost			3,000	We must go to the local market to purchase equipment for the prototype.
Miscellaneous			6,245	Assuming 10% miscellaneous cost for safety due to fluctuating prices.
Total cost (including miscellaneous costs)			71692	

1.7 Projected product lifecycle

A definition of sustainability was given by Investopedia, a financial media website headquartered in New York City that “Sustainability refers to the ability to maintain or support a process continuously over time. In business and policy contexts, sustainability seeks to prevent the depletion of natural or physical resources, so that they will remain available for the long term [11]. If our project is executed effectively, the product must be maintained and sustained going forward through updates, upgrades, customer support, etc. There is a lifetime for every electrical equipment. We either replace them or fix them if one of the devices is damaged. We will use high-quality components while creating our product to ensure a lengthy product lifespan. We will also design our product so that consumers can quickly replace any damaged parts. Our system is primarily made up of parts like a controller, a control unit, a power supply, a CCTV camera, a computer, and a traffic signal light. Since each component stands alone from the others, if one of them breaks down, a new one from the local market can be purchased and quickly installed in its place. The user would not have to worry about replacing the entire system if only one component failed. For

example, if the CCTV camera breaks down, we can easily replace it. If the damaged part is changed in this way, the expected life span of the whole system will be prolonged.

1.8 Impacts of the project

1.8.1 *Impacts on society*

An improved method of controlling traffic at junctions is a traffic density-based traffic signal control system, which dynamically alters signal timings in response to actual traffic density. The societal impacts of this system are broad and may provide a range of advantageous effects. Like:

1. **Fuel Efficiency and Emissions Reduction:** Vehicles spend less time sitting at red lights when traffic is flowing more smoothly, which improves fuel economy and lowers emissions. By reducing air pollution and greenhouse gas emissions, this has positive environmental effects.
2. **Reduced Congestion:** The technology adjusts the timing of the traffic lights based on the actual vehicle density at an intersection. As a result, there are fewer pointless pauses and starts, which reduces traffic and reduces passenger's overall travel time.
3. **Improved Travel Experience:** Due to lower waiting times at traffic signals, commuters are less irritated. Predictable traffic patterns result in more comfortable and enjoyable travel.
4. **Enhanced Safety:** The technology can adjust to shifting traffic circumstances, reducing the risk of accidents caused by sudden stops or vehicles that ignore

red signals. The level of injury and fatality results can also be decreased through improved traffic flow.

5. **Data Utilization:** The system promotes the adoption of data-driven solutions in traffic management and urban planning by depending on real-time data collecting and analysis. This raises the opportunity for smarter city planning and infrastructure.
6. **Economic Benefits:** Cost reductions for both consumers and companies are a result of reduced congestion and increased fuel efficiency. Additionally, improved transportation efficiency may benefit regional economies.

In the end, a traffic density-based traffic light control system might considerably enhance traffic flow and the overall traveling experience. To maximize its advantages and lessen any drawbacks, a comprehensive study of technological, social, and ethical considerations is necessary.

1.8.2 *Effects on environment and sustainability*

Every project or action has both positive and negative consequences on the environment, as does ours. We are going to develop a project that has some benefits and drawbacks.

- **Advantages:** This method can contribute to several ecologically advantageous outcomes by dynamically modifying traffic signal timings based on current traffic density. Reduced idle durations and fewer occurrences of stop-and-go traffic result in less stop-and-go traffic, which results in lower fuel consumption and lower greenhouse gas emissions. This leads to better air quality and less urban pollution, which improves the quality of life for locals. We used metal to

construct the prototype. As the metal will be placed on the road, it is environmentally friendly from a structural aspect. Some traffic signals use strong, bright LED lights, which adds to the light pollution that disturbs the environment at night and has an impact on animals, ecosystems, and public health. In that case, we are not using too many bright LED lights.

- **Disadvantage:** In our prototype, controlling traffic signals requires a significant amount of power. In this case, the carbon footprint of the system may vary depending on the source of the power (e.g., fossil fuels or renewable sources). We made use of things like a power supply and CCTV cameras. If any of the parts are damaged, we must replace the part. If not managed appropriately, improper disposal of outmoded technology can result in environmental pollution and electronic trash (e-waste). However, materials from these components can now be recycled due to the establishment of e-waste recycling facilities. An environmentally friendly camera composed of used plastics was created to minimize its influence on the environment. Additionally, 60% of recovered plastic is used to make sustainable monitors.

1.8.3 Health and safety issues

Every electronic device has certain safety and health concerns. We have thus highlighted the health and safety-related problems with our suggested method.

E-garbage refers to the garbage of electronic gadgets like laptops, traffic signal lights, and CCTV cameras. When used, it has no negative effects on the human body. But when this equipment becomes electronic garbage at the end of its lifetime, there are several health dangers. Lead, arsenic, and cadmium are among the heaviest hazardous elements that are released as e-waste breaks down. The plants and trees that are growing there are affected when these chemicals leach into the soil. As a result, these poisons go into the food chain of the human body, which has an impact and can

cause birth deformities and other issues. Toxins are also introduced into groundwater by persons or businesses due to improper e-waste disposal. Many surface streams, rivers, and lakes serve as the foundation for the groundwater. As a result, these poisons have the potential to harm animals and disturb the ecosystem worldwide. E-waste may have an impact on those who depend on this water. Additionally, recognized carcinogens include lead, barium, arsenic, and lithium. E-waste is very harmful to health. So, electronic waste should be disposed of by recycling. If the e-waste is proper, then this problem can be solved.

Since our prototype will be implemented on the road, we must keep an eye on people's safety. The possibility of collisions at intersections is one of the main safety concerns related to traffic lights. In case our components malfunction the safety of drivers, passengers, pedestrians, and bicycles are all in danger when signals are timed improperly or when cars run red lights. Another major issue is the safety of pedestrians, as accidents involving pedestrians might result from unclear signals. To fix these safety issues and make sure that traffic signals do their job of making the roads safer for everyone, there needs to be enough advertising, accurate signal timing, designs that are friendly to pedestrians, and driver education.

PART-B

This part includes the design, analysis and optimization of the project as prepared in
EEE400B.

Chapter 2 Project Design

2.1 Functional design

2.1.1.1 Consideration of Objective, Requirements

- i. **Accuracy:** Our prime objective is to detect the density of the road. So, the density detection accuracy must be higher. For this, the required we need to count the vehicles on the road properly.
- ii. **Price Range and Maintenance:** The device's price range must be under 72,000 BDT. Also, the device needs easy access to data at a low maintenance cost.
- iii. **Lifespan:** According to the requirements of the stakeholders, they expect a long-term lifetime.

2.1.2 Consideration of Constraints

- i. The device must have a higher level of accuracy. At this point, implementing such a device into use will be highly costly. This becomes a limitation since we must complete this project within a competitive budget.
- ii. For backup power to run the system, a battery can be installed.

2.1.3 Consideration of Health, Safety and Environmental Issues

- i. Vehicles spend less time sitting at red lights when traffic is flowing more smoothly, which improves fuel economy and lowers emissions. By reducing air pollution and greenhouse gas emissions, this has positive environmental effects.
- ii. The technology adjusts the timing of the traffic lights based on the actual vehicle density at an intersection. As a result, there are fewer pointless pauses and starts, which reduces traffic and reduces passenger's overall travel time.

- iii. Due to lower waiting times at traffic signals, commuters are less irritated. Predictable traffic patterns result in more comfortable and enjoyable travel.
- iv. The technology can adjust to shifting traffic circumstances, reducing the risk of accidents caused by sudden stops or vehicles that ignore red signals. The injury and fatality results can also be decreased through improved traffic flow.
- v. The system promotes adopting data-driven solutions in traffic management and urban planning by depending on real-time data collecting and analysis. This raises the opportunity for smarter city planning and infrastructure.
- vi. Cost reductions for both consumers and companies are a result of reduced congestion and increased fuel efficiency. Additionally, improved transportation efficiency may benefit regional economies.
- vii. The expired devices will be e-waste. All the materials or components being used should be recyclable or disposable.
- viii. We need to choose the traffic light considering the comfort of the eyes of the user.

2.1.4 Standard and Code of Practice

The focus of our project pertains to the field of traffic signaling. The provision of traffic signal manuals in Bangladesh is facilitated by the Bangladesh Road Transport Authority (BRTA). The manual provided by them has been taken into consideration for our project. Several key aspects are mentioned below.

2.1.4.1 Designing and Mounting of Signal Heads

The recommended minimum diameter for standard signal lenses is 200mm, however a diameter of 300mm is desired, particularly in the context of big and heavily trafficked intersections. The minimum diameter requirement for lenses on arrow

signals, pedestrian signals, and overhead-mounted signals is 300mm. To enhance visibility, it is recommended that the signal lamps be affixed onto a backing board of black color. Additionally, the lamps should be equipped with hoods to prevent their visibility from drivers approaching from other directions. The optimal positioning of signal heads on vertical posts involves mounting them at a height of approximately 2.3 meters above the surface of the carriageway. The appropriate positioning of the signal is adjacent to the kerb or the edge of the carriageway, while ensuring there is ample space to prevent any contact between the signal head and passing cars. The signals should be fixed overhead with the lowest edge positioned at a height of 5.7 meters above the carriageway[12]

Fig. 2.1 Traffic signals for the control of vehicular traffic at road junctions.[12]

The signal sequence is RED-AMBER-GREEN and then back to RED.

APPLICATION:

Traffic signals are used to control conflicting streams of traffic at a junction to minimize delay and reduce accidents.

VARIATION:

In cases when the signals are positioned above the carriageway, it is possible for the signal lamps to be arranged in a horizontal manner, as depicted in the illustration provided. It is important to observe that the red signal lamp should consistently be positioned at the right-hand end.

2.1.4.2 Design for overhead Camera[13]

- i. Optimal performance is obtained by maximizing camera height and centering the camera over the traffic flow as much as possible. Recommended minimum camera mounting height has been increased to 40 ft (12 m) above the detection area if the camera is centered over the roadway. Higher mounting heights (around 50 ft (15 m) or greater) are generally required if the camera is at the side of a roadway. The camera mounting height should increase as the camera is moved further from the road edge to achieve optimal performance.
- ii. Effective camera viewing distance is related to camera height. For each foot (0.3 m) of camera mounting height, viewing distance upstream and downstream of the camera location is estimated at about 10 ft (3 m) by some VIP manufacturers. Across traffic lanes, the camera can view about 2.5 ft (0.8 m) for every foot (0.3 m) of mounting height. However, conservative freeway design procedures reduce the upstream and downstream viewing distance estimate because of factors such as road configuration (e.g., elevation changes, curvature, and overhead or underpass structures), congestion level, vehicle mix, and inclement weather. Although a calibration factor or some other logic may assist in

reducing the volume error, reduction of presence and occupancy errors may be more difficult.

- iii. Select the camera location to minimize occlusion of down-lane and cross-lane vehicles. Down-lane occlusion refers to a vehicle blocked from view by a tall vehicle in front of it. Cross-lane occlusion refers to a vehicle blocked from view by a tall vehicle in a lane closer to the camera.
- iv. Select camera locations that minimize vibration and motion.
- v. Camera mounting should prevent the horizon from being visible in the horizontal or vertical fields of view. This may require a downward tilt to the camera or the installation of a sunshield.
- vi. Minimize reflections from the pavement, for example by viewing traffic approaching the camera from uphill. However, uphill traffic detection will increase the probability that headlights will shine directly into the lens at night.
- vii. Approaching nighttime traffic will produce headlight reflections from the road surface that may cause false detections. This is more likely with low camera mounting heights, under bridges, in tunnels, and on curved roadway sections.
- viii. A longer focal length lens will minimize glare entering the camera. On shorter poles, the longer focal length assists in minimizing the horizon in the field of view. For example, an 8-mm lens (as contrasted with a 6-mm lens) allows greater adjustment of the sunshield to minimize glare and the horizon. With shorter poles, aiming the camera at the lower half of trucks minimizes the horizon. A longer focal length lens also improves performance by increasing the relative size of the detection zones that are placed on the pavement.

2.1.4.3 Traffic Management Control Center (TMCC)

The building code for a Traffic Management Control Center (TMCC) can vary depending on the location and specific requirements of the region or country. However, there are general guidelines and standards that typically apply to such facilities, given their critical role in transportation infrastructure and public safety. These standards ensure that the building is safe, functional, and capable of supporting the necessary technological and operational demands. Here are some key considerations which have been adopted combinedly **American Concrete Institute (ACI- 318-19) and Bangladesh National Building Code (BNBC) 2020.**

2.1.4.3.1 Structural Integrity

- i. **Earthquake Resistance:** In seismically active areas, the building should comply with codes for earthquake resistance.
- ii. **Weatherproofing:** The structure should withstand local weather conditions, including extreme events like hurricanes or floods.

2.1.4.3.2 Security Measures

- i. **Access Control:** Secure access to prevent unauthorized entry, possibly with biometric systems.
- ii. **Surveillance Systems:** CCTV cameras for monitoring of the premises.
- iii. **Cybersecurity:** Protection against digital threats, given the sensitive nature of the data handled.

2.1.4.3.3 Power Supply and Redundancy

- i. **Uninterruptible Power Supply (UPS):** To ensure continuous operation during power outages.
- ii. **Backup Generators:** In case of prolonged power failures.
- iii. **Surge Protection:** To protect sensitive equipment from power surges.

2.1.4.3.4 Communication Infrastructure

- i. **Data Centers:** Adequate space and infrastructure for servers and IT equipment.
- ii. **Redundant Communication Lines:** To ensure continuous connectivity.

2.1.4.3.5 Operational Space Requirements

- i. **Control Room:** Ergonomically designed for efficient traffic monitoring and management.
- ii. **Meeting and Briefing Rooms:** For coordination and communication among teams.

2.1.4.3.6 Environmental Controls

- i. **HVAC Systems:** To maintain optimal temperature and air quality for both personnel and equipment.
- ii. **Acoustic Design:** Soundproofing to ensure a conducive working environment.

2.1.4.3.7 Accessibility

- i. **ADA Compliance:** Facilities should be accessible to persons with disabilities.
- ii. **Emergency Exits:** Clearly marked and easily accessible.

2.1.4.3.8 Sustainability

- i. **Energy Efficiency:** Use of energy-efficient lighting and HVAC systems.
- ii. **Water Conservation:** Implementation of water-saving fixtures.

2.1.4.3.9 Fire Safety

- i. **Fire Detection and Suppression Systems:** Including smoke detectors, sprinklers, and fire extinguishers.
- ii. **Regular Fire Drills and Safety Training** for staff.

2.1.4.3.10 Maintenance and Operations

- i. **Facilities for Staff:** Including restrooms, kitchen areas, and break rooms.

- ii. Regular Maintenance Schedule: For all systems and infrastructure.

It's important to consult with local authorities, building code experts, and architects specialized in designing such facilities to ensure full compliance with all relevant codes and standards. The TMCC is a critical facility, and as such, every aspect of its design and operation must adhere to the highest standards of safety, efficiency, and reliability.

2.1.5 Functional Block Diagram

Fig. 2.2 Functional Block Diagram.

Description of flow chart:

The image is a schematic diagram of a traffic control system. The diagram is divided into three main sections: Roadside (left), Control Center, and Roadside (right).

Roadside (left side):

- i. **Image Acquisition (via video):** This is where a camera captures real-time traffic images or video data.
- ii. The data is sent to the control center via a wireless module, as indicated by the connection between the camera, wire, and Wi-Fi module.

Control Center (center portion):

- i. **Data Send to Control Center:** This represents the flow of data from the roadside to the control center.
- ii. **Image Processing:** This includes an algorithm, a workstation, and a database, which are used to process the incoming traffic data.
- iii. **System Overdrive:** A manual override system with push buttons for direct control, presumably to change traffic light settings in case of emergencies or specific requirements.

Roadside (right side):

- i. This section includes a microcontroller and a relay, which are part of the hardware that would control the actual traffic lights.
- ii. **Traffic Light:** The final output device which displays traffic signals based on the processed data.
- iii. Feedback is sent from the control center to the traffic light, ensuring the lights change according to the processed traffic data.

The arrows indicate the flow of information and control signals between various components of the system. The overall system shows a loop where traffic conditions are monitored, processed, and then used to control the traffic lights, with the potential for manual override when necessary.

2.2 Analysis of alternate solutions

Our system is an open-ended design problem, so we will have multiple approaches to build our system. All the solutions are not based on practical implementation. These solutions might not meet all our requirements

Alternate Solution in terms of traffic detection:

To compare the solution, we have selected three parameters. Which are:

1. Power consumption
2. Accuracy
3. Cost Analysis

We have found 2 alternate solutions from the literature review that can be implemented in our project. Those are:

1. Traffic density detection by using an obstacle detection sensor.
2. Traffic density detection by using image processing:
 - a) Mixture of Gaussian (MoG) method.
 - b) You Only Look Once (YOLO) method.

2.2.1 Traffic Density Detection by using an Obstacle Detection Sensor

Technical Specification:

1. Microcontroller:

This project will need a microcontroller to function as the device's brain and coordinate the actions of all the parts. Since our device doesn't need a lot of I/O pins, we'll use an Arduino Uno for the job. The ATmega328P is the basis for the Arduino UNO microcontroller board (datasheet). It features a 16 MHz ceramic resonator (CSTCE16M0V53-R0), 6 analog inputs, 14 digital input/output pins (six of which can be used as PWM outputs), a USB port, a power jack, an ICSP header, and a reset button. It comes with everything required to support the microcontroller; all we need to do is power it with a battery or an AC-to-DC adapter or connect it to a computer via a USB cable to get going.[14]

Fig. 2.3 Arduino UNO Rev3.

2. Ultrasonic Sensor:

Ultrasonic sensors (also known as transceivers when they both send and receive, but more generally called transducers) work on a principle like radar or sonar which evaluate attributes of a target by interpreting the echoes from radio or sound waves respectively. Ultrasonic sensors generate high-frequency sound waves and evaluate the echo which is received back by the sensor. Sensors calculate the time interval between sending the signal and receiving the echo to determine the distance to an object. Systems typically use a transducer that generates sound waves in the ultrasonic range, above 18,000 hertz, by turning electrical energy into sound, then upon receiving the echo turns the sound waves into electrical energy which can be measured and displayed. Technology is limited by the shapes of surfaces and the density or consistency of the material. Foam can distort surface-level readings.[15]

Fig. 2.4 High Accuracy Ultrasonic Sensor.

Specification:

- i. Resolution up to 0.5 mm
- ii. Can realize 2 cm to 4 m non-contact ranging function, the power supply voltage is DC 5 v, working current is 2.2 mA, support GPIO communication mode.
- iii. Operating temperature: 0~+70°
- iv. Output mode: GPIO
- v. Detection angle: less than 15°
- vi. Detecting precision: 0.1cm+1%
- vii. Size: 45mm*20mm*1.2mm

2.2.1.1 Power consumption:

In this method, we will use two ultrasonic sensors in each lane to count the vehicles on the road. We will also need an Arduino microcontroller to justify the Traffic density. We will need to give the ultrasonic sensor a 5V power supply for each sensor. Each sensor draws a 2.2mA current. So, the power that each sensor consumes is = $(5 \times 2.2 \times 10^{-3}) = 0.011 \text{ W}$. We will be needing 6 sensors for a T intersection so, $(0.011 \times 6) = 0.066 \text{ W}$ power. The Arduino Nano microcontroller requires a 12V power supply and the current draws 40 mA. So, the power Arduino Nano microcontroller consumes is, $(12 \times 40 \times 10^{-3}) = 0.48 \text{ W}$. So, we will need a total power consumption of, $(0.066 + 0.48) = 0.546 \text{ W}$

2.2.1.2 Accuracy

Fig. 2.5 Sensor-detecting objects.

The working formula for an ultrasonic sensor is:

$$\text{Distance} = \frac{(\text{Time} \times \text{Speed of Sound})}{2} \quad (2.1)$$

Here's what each part of the equation means:

Distance: This is the distance between the sensor and the object.

Time: It takes time for the sound wave to travel from the sensor to the object and back.

Speed of Sound: This is the speed of sound in air, approximately 343 meters per second (m/s).

Here are some other commonly used equations for ultrasonic sensors:

$$\text{Time} = \frac{(\text{Distance} \times 2)}{\text{Speed of Sound}} \quad (2.2)$$

$$\text{Centimeters} = \frac{\frac{\text{Microseconds}}{2}}{29.1} \quad (2.3)$$

2.2.1.3 Implementation of Ultrasonic Sensor:

Fig. 2.6 Hardware implementation of Ultrasonic.

```

14:59:08.700 -> Vehicle Count:1
14:59:09.418 -> Vehicle Count:2
14:59:10.902 -> Vehicle Count:3
14:59:12.384 -> Vehicle Count:4
14:59:13.870 -> Vehicle Count:5
14:59:14.558 -> Vehicle Count:6
14:59:16.841 -> Vehicle Count:7
14:59:19.075 -> Vehicle Count:8
14:59:19.808 -> Vehicle Count:9
14:59:20.503 -> Vehicle Count:10

```

Fig. 2.7 Ultrasonic sensor vehicle detection.

Here the sensor can detect all kinds of vehicles on the road, like rickshaws, buses, cycles, cars, bikes, etc. However, we noticed that the sensor has some lacking:

- i. It could not detect the car if it was running over speed.
- ii. If the vehicle was too slow then they counted it multiple times.
- iii. When we run the device for a long time in hot weather the error increases.
- iv. After the literature review, we got to know that this device doesn't work properly in the rainy season and the fog.
- v. When any vehicle comes and stays in front of the sensor it counts continuously.
- vi. When multiple vehicles are running next to each other the sensor counts them as one.

We are required to detect the traffic density and for this, we need to count the vehicles properly. So, we can say that it doesn't fulfill our requirements.

We tested 50 vehicles on the road where the sensor accurately detected 32 and error detection was 18.

$$Accuracy = \frac{\text{Correct Results}}{\text{Total Results}} \times 100\% \quad (2.4)$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \frac{32}{50} \times 100\% \\ &= 64\% \end{aligned}$$

And,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Fault count} &= (100 - 64)\% \\ &= 36\% \end{aligned}$$

Fig. 2.8 Vehicle detection pie chart.

2.2.1.4 Cost analysis:

The cost of the Arduino microcontroller is 1100 BDT.

The cost of the Ultrasonic sensor is 220 BDT.

Total cost = 1 Arduino microcontroller + 6 Ultrasonic sensors

$$= 1100 + 6 \times (220) = 2,420 \text{ BDT}$$

2.2.2 Traffic Density Detection by using Image Processing.

Technical Specification:

i. Camera:

A camera in a density-based traffic light monitoring system serves the purpose of monitoring and analyzing the traffic density at an intersection or road segment. The camera captures real-time images or video of the traffic at an intersection. This type of system uses computer vision techniques to process the images captured by the camera and make decisions about when to change traffic signal phases.

Fig. 2.9 Camera.

ii. Laptop:

In this project, the live video data will be transferred to the laptop. The laptop will be used to process and analyze the data and after processing the laptop will give feedback to the traffic light. Here the laptop will be used in the control center from where we will control the traffic lights.

Fig. 2.10 Laptop

2.2.2.1 Accuracy:

Simulation of the system:

Fig. 2.11 Simulation of MoG

By using Mog algorithm, we tested 70 vehicles on the road where the algorithm accurately detected 57 and error detection was 13.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Accuracy} &= \frac{\text{Correct Results}}{\text{Total Results}} \times 100\% \\
 &= \frac{57}{70} \times 100\% \\
 &= 81.428\%
 \end{aligned}$$

And,

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Fault count} &= (100 - 81.428)\% \\
 &= 18.6\%
 \end{aligned}$$

Fig. 2.12 Vehicle detection pie chart.

2.2.2.2 Cost analysis:

The cost of the camera is 4500 BDT.

The cost of the laptop is 95000 BDT.

Total cost = 3 cameras + 1 laptop

$$= (3 \times 4500) + 95000$$

$$= 108,500 \text{ BDT}$$

2.2.3 Using YOLO (V5) Algorithm

YOLO, short for You Only Look Once, is a state-of-the-art real-time object detection algorithm that has revolutionized the field of computer vision. YOLO takes an image

as input and aims to predict both the class of objects present and their bounding boxes indicating their location and size. Unlike traditional object detection algorithms that require multiple processing steps, YOLO achieves this in a single forward pass through the neural network, making it incredibly fast and efficient[16].

Fig. 2.13 Simulation of YOLO.

Advantages:

- i. Speed: YOLO's single-pass processing makes it significantly faster than other object detection algorithms, enabling real-time applications like video surveillance and autonomous driving.
- ii. Accuracy: Despite its speed, YOLO boasts impressive accuracy compared to other real-time detection algorithms.
- iii. Simplicity: YOLO's architecture is relatively simple and easy to understand compared to other algorithms, making it more accessible for implementation and customization.

Though there are many advantages of YOLO, it has some limitations. To smoothly run the YOLO, we need to use a powerful GPU. YOLOv5 needs a strong GPU for both training and inference. For training, a GPU with at least 8GB of memory is suggested,

while for inference, a minimum of 4GB of memory is recommended[16], [17], [18], [19].

By using YOLO algorithm, we tested 70 vehicles on the road where the algorithm accurately detected 66 and error detection was 4.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Accuracy} &= \frac{\text{Correct Results}}{\text{Total Results}} \times 100\% \\ &= \frac{66}{70} \times 100\% \\ &= 94.285\% \end{aligned}$$

And,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Fault count} &= (100 - 94.285)\% \\ &= 5.714\% \end{aligned}$$

Fig. 2.14 Vehicle detection pie chart.

2.2.4 Comparison:

We are calculating three alternative solutions for our project. We have seen the calculation of power consumption, accuracy, and cost analysis for our system's traffic density measurement segment. If we summarize it then we get,

Table 2.1 Compare between Three Solutions.

Solution Model	Power Consumption (w)	Accuracy	Cost (BDT)
Obstacle Detection Using Ultra Sonic sensor	0.545	64%	2,420
MoG Algorithm	55	81.43%	108,500
YOLO Algorithm	55	94.29%	108,500

From the above table, we have seen that, for Traffic density detection by using an obstacle detection sensor, the cost and power consumption are low, but the accuracy is not reliable. On the other hand, Traffic density detection by using image processing works well for us, its accuracy is much better, but the power consumption and cost are quite high. Among them, the MoG algorithm accuracy is quite low compared to the YOLO algorithm.

For the traffic controlling system, we all think about safety. For safety, we need to synchronize the traffic signal properly. For proper signaling, we need to detect the traffic density more accurately. Here our preferred accuracy is shown in the image processing part using the YOLO algorithm.

So, we can say that, although the image processing system is more power-consuming and costlier than the obstacle detection sensor system, the image processing using the YOLO algorithm meets our requirements.

2.3 Refined design

2.3.1 Operational Procedure

We have opted to employ an image processing technique for traffic detection on our system after analyzing the alternative solutions.

Application/Framework Module Implemented in the project:

- i. Open CV[20]
- ii. Pygame[21]
- iii. Matplotlib[22]
- iv. Numpy[23]
- v. Pandas[24]
- vi. Yolo_v5[25]

Hardware we will use for the project:

- i. Wire
- ii. Microcontroller
- iii. Workstation (Desktop)
- iv. Camera (3pieces)
- v. Database
- vi. Push Botton

2.3.1.1 Software Working Process:

Our Python script implements a traffic monitoring and control system using computer vision techniques and serial communication for hardware interaction. Here's an overview of how your script functions:

- i. **Importing Libraries and Initializing Serial Communication:** The code imports libraries for computer vision (`cv2`), numerical operations (`numpy`), and serial communication (`serial`). It establishes a serial connection (`serial`).

Serial ('COM1', 9600)) for communication with external devices such as traffic lights.

- ii. **Setting Up Variables and Parameters:** Variables for vehicle count, threshold count, and frame size are initialized. The region of interest (ROI) for vehicle detection is defined with two y-coordinates ('roi_y_line1' and 'roi_y_line2').

Video Capture Initialization: Three video sources ('cap0', 'cap1', and 'cap2') are initialized, likely corresponding to different traffic lanes or intersections.

- i. **Main Processing Loop:**
- ii. Processing every frame from the video sources, the script goes into an endless cycle.
- iii. After resizing each frame to the specified frame size, the background subtractor is applied.
- iv. To illustrate the ROI for vehicle detection, two lines are drawn on each frame.
- v. Morphological procedures are used to minimize noise in the region extracted between these lines.

These areas have contours that help identify cars.

- i. The size of these contours is used to count the number of vehicles.
- ii. **Vehicle Counting and Traffic Light Control:**
 - The video frames show the count of vehicles in each lane, which is determined by the script.
 - The color of the traffic light (green or red) is decided by the number of vehicles.
 - Based on the number of vehicles, serial commands are delivered to apparently regulate genuine traffic lights.

Our script integrates computer vision with real-world traffic control, demonstrating a practical application of Python in intelligent transportation systems. It showcases skills in video processing, object detection, and hardware control through serial communication.

2.3.2 Hardware Working Process:

We will control the whole system with a Microcontroller. The camera will capture the live video from the road and send it through the Wi-Fi module or a wire. There will also be a Control Center, which is designed for Workstations, a Database, and a Push Button section for manual overdrive. YOLO algorithms will detect and count traffic density. Then it delivers a signal to the microcontroller after that, a relay will turn on and off the traffic light.

Fig. 2.15 A conventional T- Section.

In order to conduct testing, we have increased the density on Road 3, decreased it slightly on Road 2, and reduced it further on Road 1 and Road 2.

The density-based traffic signaling system will activate the green light at Road 3 due to its higher density. Temporarily halting all traffic on Road 2 and Road 3.

One of the stakeholders of this project has reported that Dhaka North City Corporation (DNCC) has provided detailed instructions on traffic signals. In relation to the stakeholder's criteria outlined in section 1.4.3, the maximum length of the green

light is two minutes. In order to take into consideration, the duration component, it is necessary to incorporate t-sections and 4-way intersections.

The duration of time that has been approved for our density counting will be challenged. The traffic signal will adjust its regulation in accordance with the density of vehicles.

2.3.3 Working Process of YOLO Algorithm[26], [27]

YOLO stands for You Only Look Once. The YOLO algorithm divides an image into the grid system and in that each grid detects objects within itself.

In Fig.2.16, the Structure flow chart is shown. The target detection result with marked distance is obtained by first using the CARLA client to control the CARLA server to output the image of the monocular camera and distance information. Next, mark the image and use the YOLO V5S training to obtain the weight model. Finally, combine the distance information formula.

Fig. 2.16 Structure flow chart.

Here, a technique is put forth to achieve the model's lightweight design while maintaining detection accuracy and minimizing FLOPs, parameter counts, and model size. As a result, YOLOv5s was chosen as the baseline model and enhanced. The YOLOv5s' representative structure is depicted in Fig. 1.20, and each network element is explained below.

regularization, and activation. The C3 module is made up of several structural modules referred to as bottleneck residuals. To complete residual feature transfer without deepening the output, the input of the residual structure module passes through two convolution layers before performing an add operation with the initial value. Additionally, the SPP module is the spatial pyramid pooling module that concatenates the features to fuse them and performs maximum pooling with various kernel sizes. The FPN and PAN feature pyramid structures are applied in the neck network. Strong semantic features are transferred from the top feature maps to the lower feature maps via the FPN structure. Strong localization features are also transferred from lower feature maps into higher feature maps via the PAN structure. Together, the two structures improve the neck network's capacity for feature fusion.

Fig. 2.18 Focus slice operation.

The target object's category probability, object score, and bounding box location are all output as vectors by the head end. To detect target objects of various sizes, the detection network is made up of three detection layers with varying feature map sizes. After producing the corresponding vector for each detection layer, the object in the original image is finally marked along with its predicted bounding box and category.

2.3.4 Traffic Density Detection Using YOLOv5 Algorithm

Fig. 2.19 Detection of vehicles using YOLOv5 algorithm.

Here are a few screenshots showing the YOLOv5 algorithm's traffic density detection (detailed in section 2.2.3 above). There is a Region of Interest (ROI) on the road in this system. The vehicle number that appears in the display's left corner is the number of vehicles that the system counts when they enter the ROI. When there are more than 20 cars on the road, the traffic light will automatically change, and it will also automatically change when the road is clear.

2.3.5 Simulation

Fig. 2.20 Simulated Circuit Diagram

There is a Circuit Diagram of Roadside(right) (section 2.1.4), when system get command from algorithm via serial monitor (COM1). Traffic signals tend to change their previous states, there is a microcontroller that will control the traffic signal of T-Section Road junction. There will be an Emergency Switch which will be controlled during Emergency situations. The rest of module will be controlled from the control center.

2.3.6 Py Game Simulation:

Fig. 2.21 Simulated Py Game

From fig2.19 we can see this when the traffic density is high in any road the traffic signal becomes green and when there is less traffic in any road the traffic signal becomes red. Also, we can notice that there is an amber light that helps to alert the drivers/riders that the signal will change at some time. The AMBER (or YELLOW) light indicates clearing the road when the signal is changing from green to red. If, by mistake, caught in the amber signal in the middle of a large road crossing, continue with care and do not accelerate in panic.

PART-C

This part includes the implementation, finalized design, and analysis of economic viability of the project.

Chapter 3 Demonstration of Implemented Solution and Finalization of Design

3.1 Development of the prototype

Fig. 3.1 Flowchart of Prototype.

Here, the traffic density detection process is done from live video footage. The webcam is connected to a microcontroller and will detect the density of the road using the YOLO algorithm. If the vehicle number exceeds 14, it will be considered high density. Then there will be the yellow signal for 3 seconds and the green signal for 90 seconds. Or if the number of vehicles is less than 14, it will be considered as low density. Then there will be the yellow signal for 3 seconds and the green signal for 50 seconds. When a road is green the other two roads will show a red signal. Here we named 3 different roads Road 1, Road 2, and Road 3. The YOLO algorithm will work as a loop system, at first, we will detect the density of Road1, then Road 2, and finally Road3. When Road1 starts processing the other two roads will be red signals. After the feedback from Road 1, we will start processing Road 2, at that time Road 1 and Road 3 will be red in signal. After the feedback from Road 2, we will start processing Road 3, at that time Road 1 and Road 2 will be red in signal. After the feedback from Road 3, the system will be restarted and start processing from Road 1, Road 2, and Road 3.

We have some limitations here. If the 14 vehicles are only bikes or cycles, then it doesn't need to make a green signal for 90 seconds, because it will not take that long to clear the road. We can fix this problem by adding Artificial Intelligence (AI). We consider 3 lanes in our prototype instead of 4 lanes because of insufficient graphics processing power and low budget.

We have tested the system in different combinations which are given below.

Case #1:

Fig. 3.2 Detecting Density of Road 1 and Feedback Traffic Signal.

Remark: Here we are considering Road 1, We are measuring the density of this road and showing green signal, and the other two roads are showing red signals

Case #2:

Fig. 3.3 Detecting Density of Road 2 and Feedback Traffic Signal.

Remark: Here we are considering Road 2, We are measuring the density of this road and showing green signals, and the other two roads are showing red signals.

Case #3:

Fig. 3.4 Detecting Density of Road 3 and Feedback Traffic Signal.

Remark: Here we are considering Road 3, We are measuring the density of this road and showing green signals, and the other two roads are showing red signals.

Case #4:

Fig. 3.5 Controlling Traffic Signal in Emergency Situation.

Here we are controlling the traffic signal manually, using emergency push button.

3.2 Performance evaluation of implemented solution against design requirements

The prototype has been tested and case1, case 2, case 3, case 4 show the traffic density-based traffic detection and traffic signaling process is already discussed in 3.1

Fig. 3.6 Overall Function and Set Up.

We designed the prototype according to functional requirements. The traffic signal becomes yellow for 3 seconds then green for 90 seconds when the road's density is high. If the density is low, it shows yellow for 3 seconds and green signal for 50 seconds. Therefore, the prototype satisfied the requirements to project requirements.

3.3 Finalization of design

Our design has not been modified. Our prototype was constructed using the same tools and equipment as those specified in 2.3.1. We effectively constructed our prototype by procuring the requisite components in accordance with the applicable specifications. The design we established in the previous chapter has finally been implemented as the definitive version of our system, as no modifications have been made to the system's hardware, software, peripherals, or other features. As a result, this is the final design.

3.4 Use of modern engineering tools

- i. **Visual Studio Code:** An additional integrated development environment is Visual Studio code. We also wrote our code using this IDE.
- ii. **Python IDE:** This programming language is mostly implemented using the Python IDE, integrated development environment. For writing and running our Python application, we used Python IDLE.
- iii. **Arduino IDE:** We used Arduino Nano to quickly build and test our traffic light system using components. Here Arduino IDE was used to write code to analyze and dynamically adjust traffic light timings based on traffic density

Chapter 4 Review of Milestone Achievements and Revision of Schedule

The project milestone is given below in the table,

Table 4.1 Appropriately write your caption

No	Milestones	Expected Date	Attained Date	On-Time/ Delay
1	Response collection from stakeholders	22-07-2023	02-08-2023	Delayed
2	Preparing the resource list	09-08- 2023	07-08-2023	On-Time
3	Creating project proposal paper	24-08-2023	19-08-2023	On-Time
4	Multiple solutions analysis	29-09-2023	28-09-2023	On-Time
5	Finalizing the simulation part of the project	19-10-2023	17-10-2023	On-Time
6	The formation of prototypes	12-12-2023	06-12-2023	On-Time
7	Performance evaluation of the implemented system	03-01-2024	29-04-2024	Delayed
8	Submission of design report	28-01-2024	25-05-2024	Delayed
9	Preparing final report and presentation	12-04-2024	12-06-2024	On-Time

Our project plan consists of nine milestones. A few of the goals weren't completed on schedule. By making changes to the project plan, we have remedied those milestones.

4.1.1 Remedial actions:

A few of the deadlines we had set for finishing this capstone assignment were missed.

The details are as follows:

- i. **Response collection from stakeholders:** We were unable to receive all the stakeholder responses on time due to scheduling issues, as we were operating behind schedule. In order to achieve the deadline, we must complete other predetermined tasks in advance.
- ii. **Performance evaluation of the implemented system:** Certain equipment that we were planned to utilize was unavailable. A few of them were discovered to be defective or damaged, which required their replacement. Obtaining permission was necessary due to our roadworks, and we encountered some challenges in order to performing. As a result, we were unable to accomplish the performance evaluation within the designated timeframe.
- iii. **Submission of design report:** The previous milestone required a considerable amount of time, necessitating additional time to ensure that the report was completed accurately.

Chapter 5 Cost of Solution and Economic Analysis

5.1 Bill of materials cost of solution

Bill of materials of the prototype is given below:

Table 5.1 Cost of Proposed Design

Equipment	Unit price in BDT	Quantity	Total price (Retail) in BDT
NVIDIA Jetson Nano Developer Kit (Reference RBD – 1373)	34,990[28]	1	34,990
Camera	1,050	3	3,150
USB Hub	430	1	430
Arduino Nano	390	1	390
I2C Module	140	1	140
RTC Module	260	1	260
Aluminum Heat Sink	80	1	80
Emergency Stop Push Button (AB6 – V)	20	9	180
Wire Set (Jumper wire)	55	1	55
LED	5	9	45
Resistor Set	15	3 pack	45
Miscellaneous	300	----	300
Total			40,065

We know that,

$$Retail \times 0.6 = Wholesale\ price[29] \quad (5.1)$$

So, Wholesale price of the proposed prototype is, $40,065 \times 0.6 = 24,039$ BDT

To sell the product and set up the business in the real market, we must do a detailed Economic Analysis. We have made a calculation to find the Net Present Value (NPV) of our product.

5.2 Economic analysis

For setting up the business, we must establish an office. The cost to build an office is given below.

Table 5.2 Operational Cost

Designation	Salary (per month)	No. of Employee	Total Salary (per month) in BDT
Chief Executive Officer	50,000	1	50,000
Executive officer (R & D and CTO)	35,000	4	1,40,000
Engineer	35,000	4	1,40,000
Technician	20,000	5	1,00,000
Accountant	25,000	1	25,000
Bookkeeper	15,000	1	15,000
Office Peon	10,000	1	10,000
Total			4,80,000

Office Rent and others (Electricity Bill, Water Bill and Service Charges) = 40,000 BDT

Production Cost = 24,039 BDT (per prototype).

Initially, there are 253 approaches of 70 signalized intersections[30] in Dhaka. In total, 323 traffic signals might need to be installed. So, we intend to go production for 350 of our prototypes in the first year.

So, total expenditure = $(4,80,000 + 40,000) \times 12 + (350 \times 24,039)$

$$= 1,46,53,650 \text{ BDT}$$

Initially, Product selling price = 50,000 BDT

Per year sale = $50,000 \times 500 = 2,50,00,000 \text{ BDT}$

5.2.1 Present Value Function

$$PVF(d, n) = \frac{(1 + d)^n - 1}{d(1 + d)^n} \quad (5.2)$$

Discount Rate (d) and Interest Rate (i).

Discount Rate, $d = 4\%$

Interest Rate, $I = 13\%$ [31]

Inflation Rate = 9.85% [32], [33]

So,

$$\begin{aligned} PVF(4\%, 5) &= \frac{(1 + 0.04)^5 - 1}{0.04(1 + 0.04)^5} \\ &= 4.452 \end{aligned}$$

5.2.2 Annualizing Investment:

Discount rates and interest rates are found from a well reputed bank of Bangladesh.

Annual Loan Payment,

$$\begin{aligned} A &= P \times CRF(i, n) \\ [\text{CRF} = \text{Capital Recovery Factor}] \end{aligned} \quad (5.3)$$

$$CRF(i, n) = \frac{i(1 + i)^n}{(1 + i)^n - 1} \quad (5.4)$$

$$CRF(13\%, 5 \text{ years}) = \frac{0.13(1 + 0.13)^5}{(1 + 0.13)^5 - 1} = 0.284$$

Annual Loan Payment,

$$\begin{aligned} A &= P \times CRF(i, n) \\ &= 1,46,53,650 \text{ BDT} \times 0.284 \\ &= 41,61,637 \text{ BDT} \end{aligned}$$

Annual Savings,

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta A &= \text{Per Year Sale} - \text{Annual Loan Payment} \\ &\quad - \text{Total Annual Expenditure} \end{aligned} \quad (5.5)$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= 2,50,00,000 - 41,61,000 - 1,46,53,650 \\ &= 61,84,713 \text{ BDT} \end{aligned}$$

First Cost, $\Delta P = 1,46,53,650 \text{ BDT}$

Simple Payback Period,

$$\text{simple payback period} = \frac{\Delta P}{\Delta A} \quad (5.6)$$

$$= \frac{1,46,53,6500}{61,84,713}$$

$$= 2.37 \text{ years}$$

Table 5.3 Internal Rate of Return

Life (years)	9%	11%	13%	15%	17%	19%	21%	23%	25%	27%	29%	31%	33%	35%	37%	39%
1	0.92	0.90	0.88	0.87	0.85	0.84	0.83	0.81	0.80	0.79	0.78	0.76	0.75	0.74	0.73	0.72
2	1.76	1.71	1.67	1.63	1.59	1.55	1.51	1.47	1.44	1.41	1.38	1.35	1.32	1.29	1.26	1.24
3	2.53	2.44	2.36	2.28	2.21	2.14	2.07	2.01	1.95	1.90	1.84	1.79	1.74	1.70	1.65	1.61
4	3.24	3.10	2.97	2.85	2.74	2.64	2.54	2.45	2.36	2.28	2.20	2.13	2.06	2.00	1.94	1.88
5	3.89	3.70	3.52	3.35	3.20	3.06	2.93	2.80	2.69	2.58	2.48	2.39	2.30	2.22	2.14	2.07
6	4.49	4.23	4.00	3.78	3.59	3.41	3.24	3.09	2.95	2.82	2.70	2.59	2.48	2.39	2.29	2.21
7	5.03	4.71	4.42	4.16	3.92	3.71	3.51	3.33	3.16	3.01	2.87	2.74	2.62	2.51	2.40	2.31
8	5.53	5.15	4.80	4.49	4.21	3.95	3.73	3.52	3.33	3.16	3.00	2.85	2.72	2.60	2.48	2.38
9	6.00	5.54	5.13	4.77	4.45	4.16	3.91	3.67	3.46	3.27	3.10	2.94	2.80	2.67	2.54	2.43
10	6.42	5.89	5.43	5.02	4.66	4.34	4.05	3.80	3.57	3.36	3.18	3.01	2.86	2.72	2.59	2.47
15	8.06	7.19	6.46	5.85	5.32	4.88	4.49	4.15	3.86	3.60	3.37	3.17	2.99	2.83	2.68	2.55
20	9.13	7.96	7.02	6.26	5.63	5.10	4.66	4.28	3.95	3.67	3.43	3.21	3.02	2.85	2.70	2.56
25	9.82	8.42	7.33	6.46	5.77	5.20	4.72	4.32	3.98	3.69	3.44	3.22	3.03	2.86	2.70	2.56
30	10.27	8.69	7.50	6.57	5.83	5.23	4.75	4.34	4.00	3.70	3.45	3.22	3.03	2.86	2.70	2.56

*Enter the row corresponding to project life, and move across until values close to the simple payback period, $\Delta P/\Delta A$, are reached. IRR is the interest rate in that column. For example, a 10-year project with a 5-year payback has an internal rate of return of just over 15%.

Here, the simple payback period is 2.37 years. So, according to the chart for simple payback period 2.37 years. **IRR = 31%**

5.2.3 Net Present Value (NPV):

$$NPV = \Delta A \times PVF(d, n) - \Delta P \quad (5.7)$$

$$= 61,84,713 \times 4.452 - 1,46,53,650$$

$$= 1,28,80,692 \text{ BDT}$$

After analyzing the relevant financial metrics of the project. We can observe the Net Present Value (NPV) is positive, indicating the project's future cash flow will exceed the initial investment and generate a profit. Additionally, we can note that the Internal Rate of Return (IRR) is approximately 7.75 times higher than the discount rate implying that the project will deliver an attractive return of investment. These results suggest that the project is a financial investment that is likely to yield positive outcomes.

Chapter 6 Conclusion

6.1 Verification of complex engineering problem

The project meets five complex Engineering Attributes.

6.1.1 *Depth of Knowledge Required*

- i. **K3 (Engineering Fundamental Knowledge):** This project required the utilization of an intermediate knowledge level of electronics and programming skills.
- ii. **K4 (Engineering Specialist Knowledge):** The project required expertise in machine learning specifically Convolution Neural Network (CNNs), Python programming, and embedded system design for efficient model execution.
- iii. **K5 (Engineering Design Knowledge):** To complete this project, we will need to design the system effectively. Choose the microcontroller and GPU, place sensors strategically, develop the algorithm, simulate its behaviors and test thoroughly.
- iv. **K6 (Knowledge of Modern Engineering Tools):** Gantt charts are used to visualize project schedules using Gantt projects. A CPM diagram was made using a Lucid chart. Visual Studio Code and Google Collaboration assisted in simulating the system code, identifying accuracy-related key performance metrics, and even producing vehicle-detection photos.
- v. **K8 (Research Knowledge):** The first step was a thorough analysis of the scholarly literature on vehicle detection models also expanded knowledge by exploring open-source code sources to obtain insights on real-world implementation.

6.1.2 Range of Conflicting Requirements (P2)

A classic engineering difficulty that arose during the project was balancing cost and efficiency. Although improved performance was promised, upgrading to a more potent Graphics Processing Unit (GPU) with additional RAM came at a far higher cost of production. On the other hand, the prototype's overall usefulness was hampered by using a less expensive GPU.

6.1.3 Depth of Analysis (P3)

Vehicle identification techniques were divided into two groups based on research and a review of the literature. What they mention below

- i. Model- Based Approach
- ii. Learning-Based Approach

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) were used in this project's machine learning approach for vehicle detection. Due to its innate fault tolerance, capacity for parallel processing, and capacity to generalize and deduce intricate patterns from data, CNNs do exceptionally well in this field. chose the YOLOv7 architecture in the CNN frameworks because it provides better accuracy than the other options while keeping computational complexity and cost lower.

6.1.4 Interdependence

Four subsystems comprise the design of the project[34]:

- i. Live video footage collection
- ii. Send to Graphic Processor Unit
- iii. Data Processing
- iv. Send feedback to Traffic signal.

6.2 Meeting the project objectives

The main goal of the project is to develop a density-based traffic signal system that can analyze traffic density based on current road traffic, replacing the previous Timmer-based system. Furthermore, the project aims to develop a cost-efficient intelligent traffic signal system that operates without human intervention, relying on image processing to determine traffic density. People used to endure lengthy waits during traffic jams with previous systems, but this system reduces waiting time by triggering traffic signals based on traffic density. The system has been trained, and its performance has been evaluated using the necessary modern engineering tools during the project's design phase. In order to construct the entire system. Consideration is given to numerous subsystems. The performance of the developed system was evaluated in accordance with the conditions and requirements. The design has been finalized in accordance with the performance assessment. Additionally, concerns regarding the health and safety of the tool have been considered. In conclusion, it is determined that the project is profitable after conducting a comprehensive economic analysis and examining the bill of materials. This system can be regarded as a practical, real-world solution that can be implemented to the benefit of society.

APPENDIX A. ACTIVITY CHART

Part-A

Date	Participants	Activity Description	Approx. hrs. spent
May 30, 2023	Everyone	General Discussion about proposing project	3 hrs.
May 31, 2023	Everyone	Meeting with Advisor	
Jun 02, 2023	Everyone	Proposing Topic to Advisor	
Jun 04, 2023	Everyone	Finalizing topic & meet the project requirement discussion	4 hrs.
Jun 06, 2023	Everyone	Investigating literature review according to topic	1 hr.
Jun 08, 2023	Everyone	General Discussion about proposing project	2 hrs.
Jun 14, 2023	Everyone	Discussion of Design of the project	2 hrs.
Jun 16, 2023	Everyone	Discussion about Stakeholder	1 and half hrs.
Jun 17, 2023	Everyone	Discussion about Stakeholder	1 hr.
Jun 18, 2023	Everyone	Preparing Pre defense Slide	1hr.
Jun 19, 2023	Everyone	Working on Pre defense Slide	3 and half hrs.

Jun 20, 2023	Everyone	Working on Pre defense Slide and demo presentation	4 hrs.
July 12, 2023	Everyone	Finalize Stakeholder for our project	45 minutes
July 13, 2023	Everyone	We took a break for midterm 1	6 days
July 20, 2023	Everyone	Discussion about making questionnaire for stakeholders	3 hors
July 22, 2023	Ikrum and Shahriar	Making questionnaire for the Pedestrians and Vehicle Owners/ Drivers	4 and half hrs.
July 22, 2023	Abdullah and Sonat	Making questionnaire for City Corporation/Local Municipal (DNCC/DSCC) and DTCA	5 hrs.
July 24, 2023	Ikrum and Shahriar	Making questionnaire for DMP	1 hr.
July 25, 2023	Abdullah and Sonat	Making questionnaire for BRTA	1hr.
July 29, 2023	Everyone	Study on research paper	9hrs
July 30, 2023	Everyone	Wrote Introduction	1 and half hrs.
August 2, 2023	Everyone	Study on research paper again	6hrs.
August 9, 2023	Everyone	We took a break for midterm	6days
August 14, 2023	Everyone	Taking feedback from the DNCC and DTCA	1day

August 15, 2023	Everyone	Taking feedback from the Pedestrians and Vehicle Owners/ Drivers	2days
August 21, 2023	Everyone	Taking feedback from the DSCC and DMP	1day
August 22, 2023	Everyone	Taking feedback from the BRTA	1day
August 23, 2023	Ikrum and Shahriar	Finalized literature Review.	6 hrs.
August 23, 2023	Sonat and Abdullah	Finalized literature Review.	7hrs.
August 24, 2023	Ikrum and Shahriar	Finalized literature Review.	9hrs.
August 24, 2023	Sonat and Abdullah	Finalized literature Review.	8hrs.
August 25, 2023	Shahriar	Wrote standards and codes of practice	1hr.
August 25, 2023	Everyone	Wrote Stakeholders' expectations/requirements	5hrs.
August 26, 2023	Shahriar	Justify Project requirements	1hr.
August 26, 2023	Ikrum	Made Project Plan and set milestone	3hrs.
August 27, 2023	Ikrum	Finished CPM	8hrs.

August 27, 2023	Sonat and Abdullah	Wrote Risk Management	3hrs.
August 28, 2023	Shahriar	Finished Gantt Chart	7hrs.
August 28, 2023	Sonat and Abdullah	Wrote impacts on Society	2hrs.
August 29, 2023	Ikrum and Shahriar	Finalized Resources and budget	2hrs.
August 29, 2023	Sonat	Worked on Project product lifecycle	2 and half hrs.
August 29, 2023	Abdullah	Wrote Effects on Environment and Sustainability	2hrs.
August 30, 2023	Sonat and Abdullah	Wrote health and safety issue	3hrs.
August 30, 2023	Everyone	Rechecked the whole project proposal and modified many times	5 hrs.
September 1, 2023	Everyone	Rewrote some topic by the feedback of supervisor	3days
September 4, 2023	Everyone	Corrected some issues mentioned by the supervisor	1 day
September 5, 2023	Everyone	Wrote appendix A, B and C	1 day

September 6,2023	Everyone	Finalized the report.	1day
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Part-B

Date	Participants	Activity Description	Approx. hrs. spent
Oct 05	All Members	General Discussion	2 hrs.
Oct 07	All Members & Supervisor	General Discussion with Supervisor	30 Mins.
Oct 11	All Members	Understanding Ultrasonic and IR Sensor relating to project	5 hrs.
Oct 14	Shahriar, Ikrum & Sonat	Understanding python function towards to project	3 hrs.
Oct 15	Shahriar, Ikrum & Noman	Self-taught session Python	5 hrs.
Oct 17	All members	Self- taught session Python	3 hrs.
Oct 29	Ikrum, Noman & Sonat	Self- taught session Image Processing	4 hrs.
Nov 02	All members	Self-taught session Image Processing	4 hrs.
Nov 05	All members	Self-taught session Python	3 hrs.
Nov 06	All members	Self-taught session Python	4 hrs.

Nov 07	All Members	Simulate for Ultrasonics Sensor	3 hrs.
Nov 09-17		Mid 1 Exam break	
Nov 29	Sonat	Ultrasonic sensor market survey	All day
Dec 01-22		Final Exam Break	
Dec 25	All Members	Starting Image processing Segment Simulations	8 hrs.
Dec 26	All Members	Image processing Segment Simulations	5 hrs.
Dec 27	All members	Image processing Segment Simulations	8 hrs.
Dec 28	All members	Image processing Segment Simulations	9 hrs.
Dec 31	All members & Supervisor	General meeting	
Jan 01 - 08	All members	Image processing + Report Writing	All members work individually at comfortable timeline of his own (remotely)
Jan 09		Submit draft for review	
Jan 09 – 11	All members	Catch up on all corrections	All members work

			individually at the comfortable timeline of their own (remotely)
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Part-C

Date	Participants	Activity Description	Approx. hrs. spent
Jan 28	All Members	General Discussion	3 hrs.
Feb 04	All Members	General Discussion with Supervisor	30 Mins.
Feb 07	All Members	General Discussion	2 hrs.
Feb 16-March 20	All Members	Work for simulation	
March 27-April 4	All Members	Collecting the equipment's	
April 5-14		Eid Break	
April 18-May 20	All Members	Development of prototype and report writing	
May 25- 30	All Members	Preparing slides for the final presentation	
June 2-6		Final Exam break	
June 8-11	All Members	Taking preparation for the presentation	

APPENDIX B. OTHER TECHNICAL DETAILS

At present, a diverse range of stakeholders has been identified for the capstone project. A comprehensive account of the registered stakeholders' names, accompanied by responses to select inquiries, has been incorporated. The major mode of participant involvement was traditional questioning techniques, which was opposed to our initial idea of a more digital approach. We had printed all our questionnaires and let the designated stakeholders give us their feedback. Throughout our investigation, we have gained an understanding of the aforementioned prerequisite, as previously described in Section 1.4. Throughout our conversation, we participated in an extensive discussion concerning the Dhaka Transport Co-ordination Authority (DTCA). Fortunately, a substantial portion of the discourse was devoted to the acquisition of important technological knowledge. The Bangladesh Road Transport Authority (BRTA) was not cooperative, especially the Road Safety and Operation Division. The project incorporates guidelines and codes of practice that are sourced from the "BRTA Traffic Signal Manual Volume 1."

Stakeholder Questionnaire

FOR PEDESTRIAN

1. Are you satisfied with the present traffic system?
2. Do you face any problem with this present system?
3. If you face any problem, then what is that?
4. Do you think that the present system is time-consuming?
5. Exactly when you face too much traffic on the road.
6. Do you think the present system works perfectly to reduce traffic?
7. What kind of problem do you face when any VIP movement occurs?

8. Do you face extra fuel burn for traffic?
9. On average how much time you have to spend in traffic?
10. Do you think traffic police are able to control the traffic properly?
11. Do you think that our system will help you to reduce traffic?
12. Are you willing to use the modern system?

Questionnaire for Traffic Lightning System for Vehicle Owner.

Vehicle Owners/ Drivers (Including Car, Bus, CNG, Rickshaw, Cycle, and Motorcycle)

1. How often do you use your car for daily commuting or other purposes?
2. On a scale of 1 to 5, how would you rate the current traffic situation in your area?
(1 - Very smooth and well-managed, 5 - Highly congested and chaotic)
3. Do you think the current traffic control signal system needs to be changed?
4. Have you ever encountered issues or delays at traffic lights during your commute?
If yes, please describe the problem(s)
5. How important is the synchronization of traffic lights for your overall driving experience? (1 - Not important at all, 5 - Very important)
6. Do you feel that the current traffic light system contributes to road safety in your area? (Yes/No/Maybe)
7. Have you ever experienced traffic light malfunctions, such as lights not changing or flashing incorrectly?
8. Would you prefer a more technologically advanced traffic lighting system that adapts to real-time traffic conditions?
9. How do you think a smarter traffic lighting system could benefit you as a private car owner?
10. Would you support the implementation of smart traffic lights if it helps reduce overall traffic congestion?

11. What features would you like to see in an ideal traffic lighting/signaling system as a private car owner?
12. Are you open to using mobile apps or navigation systems that provide real-time updates on traffic light timings?
13. Do you think an improved traffic lighting system would encourage more people to use public transportation or carpooling?
14. Are you concerned about the environmental impact of traffic congestion caused by inefficient traffic lights?
15. How much time, on average, do you think you spend waiting at traffic lights during your daily commute?
16. Would you be willing to provide feedback on a new traffic lighting system during its implementation and trial phase?

Questionnaires for Traffic Police

1. How long have you been serving as a traffic police officer? (years)
2. What are the primary duties and responsibilities of your role as a traffic police officer?
3. On average, how many hours per day do you spend managing traffic and enforcing road safety regulations?
4. What are the most common traffic violations you encounter in your area?
5. How effective do you think the current traffic management system is in handling traffic flow and ensuring road safety? (1 - Not effective at all, 5 - Highly effective)
6. Are there any specific areas or intersections in your jurisdiction that have a higher incidence of traffic accidents? If yes, please specify.
7. What are the most significant challenges you face while managing traffic and enforcing traffic rules?

8. How do you currently communicate and coordinate with other traffic police officers during major events or traffic incidents?
9. Are there any traffic-related issues that you believe need more attention from the authorities?
10. Do you think there is a need for technological advancements in traffic management? If yes, please provide examples.
11. How do you handle instances of aggressive driving or dealing with uncooperative drivers?
12. What measures do you think can be taken to reduce traffic congestion in your area?
13. How do you stay updated with the latest traffic regulations and changes in the law?
14. How do you handle situations involving traffic accidents and provide assistance to those involved?
15. Are you familiar with the concept of smart traffic management systems that use real-time data and automation to optimize traffic flow?
16. In your opinion, what are the potential advantages of implementing a smart traffic management system compared to the analog traffic light system?
17. Do you believe that a smart traffic management system could help reduce response times for emergency services by prioritizing their movement through traffic? (Yes/No/Maybe)
18. How important is it for traffic police to have real-time insights into traffic conditions and potential bottlenecks? (1 - Not important at all, 5 - Very important)
19. Would you prefer having access to a centralized traffic management system that allows monitoring and control of traffic lights remotely? (Yes/No/Maybe)
20. Do you think a smart traffic management system could help better manage traffic during special events or emergencies? (Yes/No/Maybe)

Questionnaire designed to gather insights from the city corporation about Traffic System

1. Please specify your role and position within the city corporation or local municipality.
2. How long has the city corporation been responsible for managing the traffic signal system in the area?
3. On a scale of 1 to 5, how would you rate the overall efficiency and effectiveness of the current traffic signal system? (1 - Inefficient and ineffective, 5 - Highly efficient and effective)
4. How often does the city corporation conduct maintenance and updates on the traffic signal system?
5. Are there any specific challenges or issues that the city corporation faces while managing the traffic signal system?
6. Does the city corporation utilize any technology or data analysis to monitor traffic flow? (Yes/No/Maybe)
7. How does the city corporation handle traffic signal timing adjustments during special events or roadwork activities?
8. Are there any plans or considerations to implement a smart traffic management system that adapts traffic signals based on real-time traffic conditions? (Yes/No/Maybe)
9. In your opinion, what are the potential benefits of transitioning from a traditional timer-based traffic signal system to a smart traffic management system?
10. How do you think a smart traffic management system could improve the overall safety and efficiency of the city's roadways?
11. Is there any collaboration or coordination between the city corporation and other relevant departments or agencies to address traffic-related issues?

12. Are there any specific areas or intersections in the city that experience recurring traffic congestion or safety concerns?
13. What steps does the city corporation take to gather feedback from residents and commuters regarding the traffic signal system's performance?
14. How important is public opinion and feedback in shaping decisions related to traffic management and signal system improvements?
15. Does the city corporation have plans to integrate the traffic signal system with other smart city initiatives or transportation management systems?
(Yes/No/Maybe)
16. What are the current funding sources for traffic signal system maintenance and upgrades?
17. Are there any challenges related to budget constraints when it comes to improving the traffic signal system?
18. How does the city corporation stay updated with advancements in traffic management technologies and best practices?
19. Are there any ongoing training programs or initiatives for city corporation staff to enhance their knowledge and skills in traffic management and signal system operation?
20. Does the city corporation have a vision or long-term plan for the future of the traffic signal system and traffic management in the area?

Questionnaire for gathering insights from the Bangladesh Road Transport Authority

1. Please specify **your role and position** within the **Bangladesh Road Transport Authority (BRTA)**
2. On a scale of 1 to 5, how would you rate the overall effectiveness of the current analog traffic system in managing traffic flow? (1 - Ineffective, 5 - Highly Effective)
3. In your experience, what are the main disadvantages of the current analog traffic system?
4. What are the most common challenges the BRTA faces while implementing the traffic rules with the current analog traffic system/rules?
5. Are you familiar with the concept of **Density-based traffic management systems** that adapt traffic signals based on real-time traffic flow? (Yes/No)
6. In your opinion, what are the potential benefits of implementing a density-based traffic management system compared to the current analog system in Bangladesh?
7. Do you believe that a density-based traffic management system could help reduce travel time for commuters and commercial vehicles? (Yes/No/Maybe)
8. What are the rules/ kind of rules you could introduce while using or implementing a Traffic Density based traffic lighting system?
9. What are some potential concerns or challenges foreseeing with the implementation of a density-based traffic management system in Bangladesh?
10. Do you think a density-based traffic management system could help optimize traffic flow at major intersections and reduce unnecessary idling? (Yes/No/Maybe)
11. Would the implementation of a density-based traffic management system require any additional training for BRTA staff? (Yes/No/Maybe)
12. Are there any specific areas or intersections in Bangladesh where you believe a density-based traffic management system would be particularly beneficial? If yes, please specify

- 13.** How important is it for the BRTA to receive prior notification or updates about traffic conditions, especially during peak hours or special events? (1 - Not important at all, 5 - Very important)

Questionnaire for Dhaka Transport Co- ordination Authority

1. Could you tell us your name and designation please?
2. Could you please provide us with your responsibilities?
3. What kind of work in a city does DTCA do?
4. How does DTCA coordinate the transport works in Dhaka city?
5. How do you rate the efficiency of the present traffic signal system (fixed timer) in traffic congestion management? (Poor-1, Very good – 5)
6. Does DTCA have any acquaintance with density-based traffic signaling?
7. Is there any plan to set up rules /guidelines for smart traffic signaling?
8. Does DTCA have any plan to introduce smart traffic signaling?
9. What level of integration is required between various traffic signaling installation and the controlling system for density based approach to work effectively?
10. Are there any concerns about public awareness and acceptance of the new signaling system? What strategies does DTCA have to communicate such changes to the public and address the major potential concerns?
11. Would you allow any entity to assess some roads of Dhaka for the sake of research (in a closed controlled environment) with a smart traffic management system?

APPENDIX C. JUSTIFICATION OF COMPLEX ENGINEERING PROBLEM

This table prepared in EEE400A justifies the proposed project as a complex engineering problem

Attribute	Complex Engineering Problems have characteristic P1 and some or all of P2 to P7:	Covered in the project? (Y/N)	Explain/justify
Depth of knowledge required	P1: Cannot be resolved without in-depth engineering knowledge at the level of one or more of K3, K4, K5, K6 or K8, which allows for a fundamentals-based, first principles analytical approach	Y	<p>Project Engineering Knowledge Overview</p> <p>K3 (Engineering Fundamental Knowledge):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requires intermediate electronics and programming skills. <p>K4 (Engineering Specialist Knowledge):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requires expertise in machine learning, specifically CNNs, Python programming, and embedded system design. <p>K5 (Engineering Design Knowledge):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requires effective system design, including microcontroller and GPU selection, sensor placement, algorithm development, and thorough testing. <p>K6 (Knowledge of Modern Engineering Tools):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uses Gantt charts, Lucid chart, Visual Studio Code, and Google Collaboration for project visualization, simulation, and performance metrics identification. <p>K8 (Research Knowledge):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Thorough analysis of scholarly literature and exploration of open-source code sources for real-world implementation insights.
Range of conflicting requirements	P2: Involves wide-ranging or conflicting technical, engineering and other issues	Y	<p>Project Engineering Challenges</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Balancing cost and efficiency. • Upgrading GPU with additional RAM at higher production cost.

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prototype's usefulness hindered by less expensive GPU.
Depth of analysis required	P3: There is no obvious solution, and abstract thinking and originality in analysis are required to formulate suitable models	Y	<p>Vehicle Identification Techniques Overview</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Model-Based Approach: Utilizes Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) for vehicle detection. • Learning-Based Approach: Uses machine learning for detecting intricate patterns. • CNNs excel due to fault tolerance, parallel processing, and pattern generalization. • YOLOv7 architecture chosen for better accuracy, lower computational complexity, and cost.
Familiarity of issues	P4: Involves infrequently encountered issues	N	
Extent of applicable codes	P5: Are outside problems encompassed by standards and codes of practice for professional engineering	N	
Extent of stakeholder involvement and conflicting requirements	P6: Involves diverse groups of stakeholders with widely varying needs	N	
Interdependence	P7: High level problems including many component parts or sub-problems	Y	<p>Project Design Subsystems:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Live video footage collection. • Send to Graphic Processor Unit. • Data processing. • Send feedback to Traffic signal.

APPENDIX D. JUSTIFICATION OF COMPLEX ENGINEERING ACTIVITIES

This table prepared in EEE400C describes the complex engineering activities in the project

Attribute	Complex activities mean (engineering) activities or projects that have some or all of the following characteristics:	Covered in the project? (Y/N)	Explain
Range or resources	A1: Involves the use of diverse resources (for this purpose, resources include people, money, equipment, materials, information and technologies)	Y	Project Prototype Development <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Built using multiple modules, equipment, and devices. • Requirements determined based on stakeholder information. • Utilizes modern technologies like deep learning and traffic detection. • System application centered around stakeholders.
Level of interaction	A2: Requires resolution of significant problems arising from interactions among wide-ranging or conflicting technical, engineering, or other issues	Y	Project Subsystems and Their Impact <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multiple sub-systems are significant in the project. • Overload of work from these sub-systems slows system processing. • Ultra Sonic sensor could have made cost more efficient, but compromised system performance.
Innovation	A3: Involves creative use of engineering principles and research-based knowledge in novel ways	Y	Unique YoLOv5 Method Proposal <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unique research method. • Limited research in our country and globally.
Consequences for society and the environment	A4: Has significant consequences in a range of contexts; characterized by difficulty of prediction and mitigation	Y	Bangladesh's High Population Challenges <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Difficulty in manual traffic signal operation. • Device aids in reducing road traffic.
Familiarity	A5: Can extend beyond previous experiences by applying principles-based approaches	Y	Implementing Convolutional Neural Network in Deep Learning <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implemented in a field not academically expertise. • Crucial for Traffic Detection. • Learned and used CNN in a sub-system.

APPENDIX E. RUBRICS

Rubrics for EEE400

Table 1: Rubrics for assessment of PO9 (Individual work and teamwork)

Performance indicators	Outstanding (9 – 10)	Good (7 – 8)	Satisfactory (6)	Unsatisfactory (0 – 5)
Individual skills	Actively participates in group discussions and decision making, contributes useful ideas, completes assigned responsibilities thoroughly on time	Participates in group discussions and decision making, contributes ideas, completes assigned responsibilities mostly on time	Somewhat participates in group discussions and decision making, sometimes contributes ideas, completes some of the assigned responsibilities on time	Does not participate in group discussions and decision making, does not contribute relevant ideas, does not complete assigned responsibilities on time
Team skills	Always collaborates with others, always promotes constructive team atmosphere, always identifies and responds to conflicts promptly and positively	Usually collaborates with others, usually promotes constructive team atmosphere, usually identifies and responds to conflicts positively	Sometimes collaborates with others, sometimes promotes constructive team atmosphere, sometimes identifies and responds to conflicts positively	Does not collaborate with others, does not promote constructive team atmosphere, does not identify and respond to conflicts
Leadership skills	Always provides direction to achieve goals, always respects and listens to other members, always plans for improvement, always motivates others	Usually provides direction to achieve goals, usually respects and listens to other members, usually plans for improvement, usually motivates others	Sometimes provides direction to achieve goals, sometimes respects and listens to other members, sometimes plans for improvement, sometimes motivates others	Does not provide direction to achieve goals, does not respect and listen to other members, does not plan for improvement, does not motivate others
Multidisciplinary activities	Fully understands and appreciates the multidisciplinary nature of the project activities, shows interests and participates in activities in disciplines outside of own	Mostly understands and appreciates the multidisciplinary nature of the project activities, participates in activities in disciplines outside of own	Somewhat understands and appreciates the multidisciplinary nature of the project activities, participates in some activities in disciplines outside of own	Does not understand or appreciate the multidisciplinary nature of the project activities, does not participate in activities in disciplines outside of own

Table 2: Rubrics for assessment of PO8 (Ethics)

Performance indicators	Outstanding (9 – 10)	Good (7 – 8)	Satisfactory (6)	Unsatisfactory (0 – 5)
Equity	Always approaches situations with consideration of equity, always behaves inclusively	Mostly approaches situations with consideration of equity, mostly behaves inclusively	Sometimes approaches situations with consideration of equity, Sometimes behaves inclusively	Does not approach situations with consideration of equity, does not behave inclusively
Accountability	Always understands about accountability and personal responsibility, always assumes responsibility of own actions	Mostly understands about accountability and personal responsibility, mostly assumes responsibility of own actions	Sometimes understands about accountability and personal responsibility, sometimes assumes responsibility of own actions	Does not understand about accountability and personal responsibility, does not assume responsibility of own actions
Proper use of others' works	Always recognizes the need for due acknowledgment of others' works, intellectual property and copyrighted materials, and acts accordingly	Mostly recognizes the need for due acknowledgment of others' works, intellectual property and copyrighted materials, and mostly acts accordingly	Sometimes recognizes the need for due acknowledgment of others' works, intellectual property and copyrighted materials, and sometimes acts accordingly	Does not recognize the need for due acknowledgment of others' works, intellectual property and copyrighted materials, and does not act accordingly
Professionalism	Fully understands the role of the engineer in protecting public interests, fully understands and is aware of relevant codes of ethics	Mostly understands the role of the engineer in protecting public interests, mostly understands and is mostly aware of relevant codes of ethics	Somewhat understands the role of the engineer in protecting public interests, somewhat understands and is somewhat aware of relevant codes of ethics	Does not understand the role of the engineer in protecting public interests, does not understand or is not aware of relevant codes of ethics

Rubrics for EEE400A

Table EEE400A: Rubrics for assessment of the project concept and proposal

Performance indicators	Outstanding (9 – 10)	Good (7 – 8)	Satisfactory (6)	Unsatisfactory (0 – 5)
PCP_PI1: Able to identify a suitable complex engineering design problem (1a) [sec-1.1, Appendix C] (CO1/PO12, P1)	Demonstrates an ability to explore a topic thoroughly, and to identify a suitable complex engineering problem	Demonstrates an ability to explore a topic, and to identify a reasonably suitable complex engineering problem	Demonstrates an ability to somewhat explore a topic, and to identify a somewhat suitable complex engineering problem	Demonstrates minimal or no ability to explore a topic, or to identify a suitable complex engineering problem
PCP_PI2: Engages to stay up to date on the relevant topic (2b) [sec-1.2] (CO1/PO12, P1)	Demonstrates thorough engagement to stay up to date on the relevant topic	Demonstrates engagement to stay up to date on the relevant topic	Demonstrates some engagement to stay up to date on the relevant topic	Demonstrates minimal or no engagement to stay up to date on the relevant topic
PCP_PI3: Identifies the regulatory requirements, standards, and codes of practice (2a) [sec-1.1] (CO2/PO3, P5)	Identifies all the relevant regulatory requirements, standards, and codes of practice	Identifies most of the relevant regulatory requirements, standards, and codes of practice	Identifies some of the relevant regulatory requirements, standards, and codes of practice	Does not identify any of the relevant regulatory requirements, standards, and codes of practice
PCP_PI4: Explains the objectives, project requirements and constraints of the solution considering the expectations of the stakeholders (2c) [sec-1.4, 1.5] (CO2/PO3, P2, P6)	Clearly explains the objectives, project requirements and constraints taking into account all the expectations of the stakeholders	Explains the objectives, project requirements and constraints taking into account most of the expectations of the stakeholders	Somewhat explains the objectives, project requirements and constraints fully taking into account some the expectations of the stakeholders	Does not explain the objectives, project requirements and constraints and/or does not take into account any expectation of the stakeholders
PCP_PI5: Prepares project management plan, setting up milestones and considering risks and contingencies (2d) [sec-1.6.1, 1.6.1.1] (CO3/PO11)	Prepares a comprehensive project management plan, clearly sets up milestones, thoroughly considers risks and contingencies	Prepares a project management plan, sets up milestones, considers risks and contingencies	Prepares a project management plan, sets up a few milestones, attempts to consider risks and contingencies	Prepares a unclear/incomplete project management plan, does not set up milestones, does not consider risks and contingencies
PCP_PI6: Identifies required resources and prepares a realistic budget (2e, 2g) [sec-1.6.3] (CO3/PO11)	Identifies all resources and prepares budget that covers all applicable areas of the project including room for contingency	Identifies most resources and prepares budget that covers most applicable areas of the project including room for contingency	Identifies some resources and prepares budget that covers some applicable areas of the project	Cannot identify resources and cannot prepare a budget addressing major applicable areas of the project

PCP_PI7: Explains how to sustain and maintain the product/service in business if the solution is successfully commercialized. (2h) [sec-1.7]	Clearly explains how to sustain and maintain the product/service in business if the solution is successfully commercialized.	Explains how to sustain and maintain the product/service in business if the solution is successfully commercialized.	Somewhat explains how to sustain and maintain the product/service in business if the solution is successfully commercialized.	Does not explain how to sustain and maintain the product/service in business if the solution is successfully commercialized.
PCP_PI8: Considers the impact of the solution on society including health, safety, cultural, and legal issues (2f) [sec-1.8.1, 1.8.3] (CO4/PO6)	Considers all the impacts on society including health, safety, cultural and legal issues	Considers most of the impacts on society including health, safety, cultural and legal issues	Considers some of the impacts on society including health, safety, cultural and legal issues	Does not consider any impact on society including health, safety, cultural and legal issues
PCP_PI9: Considers the impact of the solution on environment and sustainability over the entire product life cycle. Proposes mitigating solution if needed. (2f) [sec-1.8.2] (CO5/PO7)	Considers all the impacts on environment and sustainability. If necessary, proposes solutions to mitigate negative impact	Considers most of the impacts on environment and sustainability. If necessary, identifies impacts which need mitigation	Considers some of the impacts on environment and sustainability	Minimal or no consideration of impacts on environment and sustainability

- P1:** Cannot be resolved without in-depth engineering knowledge at the level of one or more of K3, K4, K5, K6 or K8, which allows for a fundamentals-based, first principles analytical approach
- P2:** Involves wide-ranging or conflicting technical, engineering and other issues
- P4:** Involves infrequently encountered issues
- P6:** Involves diverse groups of stakeholders with widely varying needs

Rubrics for EEE400B

Table 1: Rubrics for assessment of the Design Report

Performance indicators	Outstanding (9 – 10)	Good (7 – 8)	Satisfactory (6)	Unsatisfactory (0 – 5)
DR_PI1: Develops a functional design considering applicable standards, codes of practice, health, safety, and environmental considerations. (1a) [sec-2.1] (CO2/PO3, P2, P7)	Appropriately partitions the problem into sub-problems, considers all relevant engineering standards and codes where applicable, involves all health, safety, and environmental issues in design	Partitions the problem into sub-problems, considers most relevant engineering standards and codes where applicable, involves major health, safety, and environmental issues in design	Partitions the problem into sub-problems to some extent, considers some relevant engineering standards and codes where applicable, involves some health, safety, and environmental issues in design	Does not usefully partition the problem into sub-problems, does not consider relevant engineering standards and codes, health, safety, and environmental issues not involved in design
DR_PI2: Formulates and evaluates alternate solutions (1b) [sec-2.2] (CO1/PO2, P1, P3)	Effectively formulates multiple solutions that functionally meet most requirements, compares and evaluates alternate solutions, extracts valid conclusions	Formulates multiple solutions that functionally meet most requirements, partially compares and evaluates alternate solutions, conclusions in line with analysis	Formulates multiple solutions that functionally meet some requirements, attempts to compare and evaluate alternate solutions, conclusions somewhat in line with analysis	Does not formulate multiple solutions, no attempt to compare and evaluate alternate solutions, conclusions not based on analysis
DR_PI3: Prepares and refines design with analysis and/or simulation of the system for implementation (1c, 1d) [sec-1.1] (CO2/PO3, P1)	Performs all design calculations, produces detailed design, analyzes and/or simulates to verify that the design satisfies all requirements. Design is skillfully refined to facilitate implementation.	Performs most design calculations, produces design with some details, analyzes/simulates to verify that the design satisfies most requirements. Design is refined to facilitate implementation.	Performs some design calculations, produces design with a few details, attempts to analyze/simulate the design to verify satisfaction of requirements. Design is somewhat refined to facilitate implementation.	Does not perform design calculations, detailed design not produced, analysis/simulation not done to verify satisfaction of requirements. Design is not refined to facilitate implementation.

- P1:** Cannot be resolved without in-depth engineering knowledge at the level of one or more of K3, K4, K5, K6 or K8, which allows for a fundamentals-based, first principles analytical approach
- P2:** Involves wide-ranging or conflicting technical, engineering and other issues
- P3:** There is no obvious solution, and abstract thinking and originality in analysis are required to formulate suitable models
- P7:** High level problems including many component parts or sub-problems

Rubrics for EEE400C

Table 1: Rubrics for Final report of EEE400C

Performance indicators	Outstanding (9 – 10)	Good (7 – 8)	Satisfactory (6)	Unsatisfactory (0 – 5)
FR_PI1: Discusses how the prototype of the solution is developed. [sec 3.1]	Comprehensively discusses how the prototype of the solution is developed with the help of appropriate figures, photos and diagrams	Discusses how the prototype of the solution is developed with the help of appropriate figures, photos and diagrams	Somewhat discusses how the prototype of the solution is developed with the help of appropriate figures, photos and diagrams	Poorly discusses how the prototype of the solution is developed with the help of appropriate figures, photos and diagrams
FR_PI2: Evaluates performance of the developed system as per requirements. Finalizes design based on performance evaluation (1a and 1b) [sec 1.1, sec 3.3] (CO1/PO4, CO3/PO3)	System meets all requirements or the students can identify and explain clearly when deviation from requirements occurs. Revises design with appropriate technical analysis if necessary to achieve compliance with all specification and requirements	System meets major requirements. Students can identify and explain most deviations from requirements. Revises design with technical analysis if necessary to achieve compliance with most specification and requirements	System meets some requirements. Students can identify and explain some deviations from requirements. Revises design with some technical analysis if necessary to achieve compliance with some specification and requirements	System does not meet most requirements. Students cannot identify and explain most deviations from requirements. Design not revised to achieve compliance.
FR_PI3: Finalizes design based on performance evaluation (1c) [sec 3.3] (CO3/PO3)	Revises design with appropriate technical analysis to achieve compliance with all requirements finalized in 400B	Revises design with technical analysis to achieve compliance with most requirements finalized in 400B	Revises design with some technical analysis to achieve compliance with some requirements finalized in 400B	Does not revise design with technical analysis to achieve compliance with any requirement finalized in 400B
FR_PI4: Selects and uses appropriate modern engineering tools for modeling, simulation and/or performance evaluation throughout the project (EEE400 A, B, C) [sec 3.4] (CO2/PO5)	Carefully selects and skillfully uses modern engineering tools knowing all the relevant limitations of the tools	Selects and uses modern engineering tools with some degree of care and skill knowing major relevant limitations of the tools	Selects and uses modern engineering tools knowing some relevant limitations of the tools	Selected and used modern engineering tools are mostly not appropriate. No knowledge of relevant limitations of the tools
FR_PI5: Achieve the milestones set in the project proposal or	All milestones are reached on time or corrective measures	Most milestones are reached on time or corrective measures	Milestones are somewhat reached on time or some	Milestones are mostly not reached on time. Corrective measures

revises the schedule appropriately to complete the project within the deadline (EEE400 A, B, C) [Chapter 4] (CO4/PO11)	are appropriately taken to revise the schedule to complete the project within deadline	are taken to revise the schedule to complete the project within deadline	corrective measures are taken to revise the schedule to complete the project within deadline	are not taken to revise the schedule to complete the project within deadline
FR_PI6: Prepares the bill of materials and estimates the cost of the system [sec 5.1] (CO5/PO11)	Prepares bill of materials considering all the project components and/or parts and the cost is accurately estimated	Prepares bill of materials considering most the project components and/or parts and the cost is estimated	Prepares bill of materials considering major project components and/or parts and the cost is reasonably estimated	Prepares bill of materials ignoring important project components and/or parts and the cost is not reasonable
FR_PI7: Performs economic analysis to calculate suitable economic parameter(s) to evaluate the economic prospect of the proposed project [sec 5.2] (CO5/PO11)	Evaluates the financial prospect of the project through detailed and thorough analysis. Interpretation is clear	Evaluates the financial prospect of the project through analysis. Provides interpretation	Evaluates the financial prospect of the project through analysis.	Does not evaluate the financial prospect of the project through analysis

Table 2: Overall rubrics on report writing

Communicates the main ideas in written form [Overall] (CO8/PO10)	Communicates the main ideas clearly and to the point	Communicates the main ideas	Communicates the main ideas to some extent	Does not communicate the main ideas
Uses illustrations (graphs, tables, diagrams) to support ideas, analysis and interpretation [Overall] (CO8/PO10)	Skillfully uses illustrations to support ideas. Illustrations enhance comprehension of analysis and interpretation	Uses illustrations to support ideas. Illustrations somewhat enhance comprehension of analysis and interpretation	Uses illustrations which are related to analysis and interpretation	Either does not use illustrations or illustrations used are not relevant to ideas, analysis and interpretation
Uses citations and references [Overall] (CO8/PO10)	Citations and references are effectively used to duly acknowledge prior art and other people's works	Citations and references are used to acknowledge prior art and other people's works	Citations and references are used to somewhat acknowledge prior art and other people's works	Citations and references are not used or prior art and other people's works are not acknowledged
Uses a language which is mechanically (punctuation, spelling and grammar) correct [Overall] (CO8/PO10)	The report is free from mechanical errors	The report contains a few mechanical errors	The report contains some mechanical errors	The report contains several mechanical errors

Table 3: Rubrics for oral presentation

Performance indicators	Outstanding (9 – 10)	Good (7 – 8)	Satisfactory (6)	Unsatisfactory (0 – 5)
Communicates appropriately targeting the society at large (CO8/PO10)	Communication is skillfully tailored to appropriately suit the level of target audience	Communication is tailored to suit the level of target audience	Communication is somewhat tailored to suit the level of target audience	Communication is not tailored to suit the level of target audience
Focusses on the creative aspects of the solution with clarity (CO8/PO10)	Creative aspects are clearly articulated and emphasized. Presentation is logically and skillfully structured	Creative aspects are articulated and emphasized. Presentation structure is logical	Creative aspects are somewhat articulated and emphasized. Presentation structure is somewhat logical	Creative aspects are not articulated or emphasized. Presentation structure is not logical
Above two PIs will assess the sales pitch part of the presentation. Following PIs are for the technical part				
Designs and integrates visual aids (illustrations, demonstrations, props, etc) to support and focus presentation (CO8/PO10)	Visual aids are creatively designed, skillfully used and seamlessly integrated to enhance and focus presentation	Visual aids are designed, used and integrated to enhance and focus presentation	Visual aids are designed, used and integrated to enhance and focus presentation to some extent	Visual aids are not designed, used or integrated to enhance and focus presentation
Completes presentation within the allotted time (CO8/PO10)	Finishes the presentation as prepared within time without rushing or skipping content	Finishes the presentation as prepared within time with rushing or skipping content occasionally	Finishes the presentation as prepared within time with rushing or skipping content a few times	Does not finish the as prepared presentation within time or skips major contents to finish within time
Listens to the questions and answers appropriately (CO8/PO10)	Carefully listens to the questions, answers concisely transitioning skillfully between presentation and Q/A	Listens to the questions, answers to the point transitioning well between presentation and Q/A	Listens to the questions, answers somewhat to the point transitioning between presentation and Q/A in an acceptable manner	Does not listen to the questions, answers not to the point transitioning between presentation and Q/A not in an acceptable manner

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